

Hyper-**N**etwork for **e**lectro**M**obility

NeMo D8.6 Proceedings of the NeMo Final Event

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Glossary of terms

Term	Description
Actor	All physical or digital entities of the electromobility domain which may interact with the Hyper-Network. They can be drivers and owners of EVs, vehicle manufacturers, Charge point owners or operators, energy suppliers, DSOs, service providers, public authorities, policy makers, municipalities, regulatory bodies, customers' associations.
BAEM	The Business Alliance for Electromobility, as the not-for profit association based on yearly membership fee that will take over the NeMo results and the management of the Hyper-Network.
Business Object	A Business Object describes a basic data structure that is used within a Business Scenario.
Electromobility or e-mobility	The use of electric-powered drivetrains for road vehicles designed to shift vehicle design away from the use of fossil fuels and carbon gas emissions.
e-roaming or eRoaming	A market model in electro mobility whereby EV drivers may charge their vehicles at all charging stations, regardless of any contracts concluded with operators. The billing then takes place via the customer's own contractual partner.
Hyper-Network	A distributed environment developed by the NeMo project with open architecture based on standardised interfaces, in which actors (physical or digital) can connect and interact seamlessly, exchange data and provide integrated and interoperable ICT services.
Hyper-Network Business partner	A user of the Hyper-Network which NeMo or the BAEM has accredited as being compliant with the relevant protocols and procedures. Potentially a "label" that could be used by the organisation concerned.
NeMo Node	The IT package containing all NeMo components and allowing the technical and business connection to the Hyper-Network

List of abbreviations and acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
ACEA	European Automobile Manufacturers Association
API	Application Program Interface
BAEM	Business Alliance for Electromobility
B2B	Business to Business
B2C	Business to Customer
CIM	Common Information Models
CP	Charge Point
CPO	Charge Point Operator
DSO	Distribution System Operator
EMSP	ElectroMobility Service Provider
EV	Electric Vehicle
ISO	International Organization for Standardization
OCPP	Open Charge Point Protocol
OEM	Original Equipment Manufacturer (Automotive)
OWL-s	Web Ontology Language
SoC	Status of Charge
SOH	State of Health
V2G	Vehicle to Grid

Executive Summary

The current document reports about the organisation, the presentations and discussions that were made during the Final Conference and Exhibition of the NeMo project, that was organised in Barcelona, Spain, on Thursday, 19 September 2019.

Concluding three years of research and development, the consortium showcased how NeMo makes Electromobility in the road sector more attractive for businesses and users. The NeMo Final Event and Exhibition brought together industry and e-roaming platforms representatives, academics and researchers, road, charging point and grid operators, solution providers and other Electromobility stakeholders, to share the project results leading to the node-based Hyper Network for Electromobility, the functionalities that it offers and its contribution towards seamless, interoperable and widely available services for all Electromobility actors.

Through a number of technical presentations, panel discussions, interactive demonstrations and hands-on sessions, prominent speakers from academia and industry as well as renowned experts in the field presented the key elements of the NeMo Hyper-Network. These elements include the NeMo Common Information Models, easy creation, execution and delivery of services on the Hyper-Network, as well as the smart horizontal services that NeMo has made available. In parallel, the Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol, which links different Electromobility roaming platforms and enables cross-provider Electromobility roaming seamlessly, was presented and the specific architecture developed for the Extended Vehicle and Neutral Server deployed via the project's OEMs, which assists the driver to experience improved services and access real vehicle data, will be presented to the attendees.

The conference brought together 75 participants from small and medium-sized companies based mainly in Barcelona, representatives of consortia responsible for the implementation of European funded projects related with electromobility, as well as representatives of the municipality of Barcelona and ordinary citizens.

In the concluding panellist discussion, the key points for the future were summarised as: the needed collaboration by all actors as promoted by NeMo, the necessity for energy management, security, the provision of an easy and seamless experience for drivers, smart and fun services offer and battery manufacturing issues.

1. Introduction

1.1 Scope of the document

This document deeds a report of the actions made (preliminary actions also included) within T8.3 as regards the organisation of the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition. Moreover, it includes the presentations made by the NeMo partners during the event, the discussions and questions risen by the audience and the conclusions of the discussions among the experts.

1.2 Intended Audience

Table 1: Intended Audience

Intended audience	Reasons for reading this document
NeMo Project partners	to be informed about the actions made before the event, the discussions and presentations made during the event, its outcomes and overall have a common view of the effort spent for its successful realisation
European Commission	this is a deliverable of the NeMo project and reports about the discussions and presentations made during the Final Conference and Exhibition of the project
Target Groups: <i>electromobility sector, businesses, charge point operators, electric grid operators, battery manufacturers</i>	to share knowledge, information and vision around the electromobility sector in general and about interoperability of electromobility services and raise awareness on the topic
Representatives involved into similar projects	to share knowledge, information and vision in the electromobility sector in general and about interoperability of electromobility services
Anyone interested	to share knowledge, information, vision related to the project's topic, raising visibility in wider audience and in general contributing to raising awareness around electromobility topics in Europe.

1.3 Methodology

The creation of this deliverable was based on the close collaboration among the task leaders and ICCS team in order to ensure that all related information around the preparation and implementation of the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition have been reported and presented within the current document. Moreover, to ensure that all information regarding the discussions and presentations made during the event were properly collected and presented in detail to the reader of this deliverable in an easy-to-read manner, four pro forma templates were created beforehand as showed in **Annex IV**.

1.4 Structure

The document consists of 4 chapters and 4 appendices. The **first chapter** presents the scope of the deliverable, the audience that is addressed to and its structure. The **second chapter** provides an overview of the activities performed for the preparation of the event and the **third chapter** reports the activities on the conference day. The **fourth chapter** serves the main scope of this deliverable as described in the DoA which is respectively a brief report on the discussions made during the event.

In **Annex I**, the reader can find the original invitation letter from the project coordinator sent to NeMo stakeholders. In **Annex II**, the press invitation in English and Spanish is reported, in **Annex III** the official Agenda that was distributed to the participants of the event is shown. In **Annex IV**, the pro-forma templates used as a methodology for collecting information during the conference proceedings are presented. Lastly, in **Annex V** the original presentations of the conference's speakers are available to the reader.

2. Preliminary Activities

NeMo partners have put a lot of effort in order to successfully organize the Final Conference and Exhibition, raise its visibility, attract press attention, invite stakeholders to participate at the event and overall attract representatives from the electromobility sector.

2.1 Press Invitation

A press invitation was initially created in English version by **ERTICO** and distributed to their network and to the partners' networks. Later on, it was translated in Spanish by the **Municipality of Barcelona** that together with Mosaic distributed it in their network in Spain with main focus to contacts located in Barcelona region. Screenshots of the original press invitation (EN, ES) can be found in **Annex II**.

2.1.1 Press Invitation content (EN)

Table 2: Press Invitation content in English

Press Invitation Content in English

The partners of the European Horizon 2020 project NeMo “Hyper-Network for Electromobility” are pleased to invite you to the project’s Final Conference and Exhibition, taking place in Barcelona, Spain, on Thursday, 19 September 2019.

As the NeMo project reaches its conclusion, this conference will present the result of three years of work by the consortium partners through technical presentations and a technology showcase featuring live demonstrations of electromobility services.

The conference will be introduced by a representative of the City of Barcelona, host of the event, who will give an overview of electromobility in the city.

The event agenda will feature in-depth presentations of:

- The NeMo Hyper-Network: What it is and how it works
- The Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol
- Access to the NeMo Hyper-Network and business features of the NeMo Marketplace
- Followed by a panel discussion: “The future of electromobility”

In addition to the Conference programme, participants will be able to visit an exhibition area showcasing different aspects of NeMo. Live demonstrations will include:

- NeMo, the Block Chain-based Hyper-Network
- The NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node
- Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure
- End-to-end smart charging based on ISO 15118 and OCPP
- NeMo Battery Services, Service creation in the Hyper-Network

The demonstrations will be accompanied by a series of technical posters.

The language of the conference is English.

We are happy to answer your queries and arrange interviews for you. For all queries, please contact Hugo Roebroek, NeMo Dissemination Manager, at h.roebroek@mail.ertico.com or +32 473 516 112.

Event registration and updates: <https://www.eventbrite.com/e/from-project-to-market-seamlesselectromobility-services-in-europe-registration-61996854260>

For more information, visit <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>

2.1.2 Press Invitation content (ES)

Table 3: Press Invitation content in Spanish

Press Invitation Content in Spanish

A los socios del proyecto europeo Horizonte 2020 NeMo “Hyper-Network for Electromobility” les complace invitarlo a la Conferencia y Exposición Final del proyecto, que tendrá lugar en Barcelona, España, el jueves 19 de septiembre de 2019.

A medida que el proyecto NeMo se acerca a su conclusión, esta conferencia presentará el resultado de tres años de trabajo de los socios del consorcio a través de presentaciones técnicas y una exhibición tecnológica con demostraciones en vivo de servicios de electromovilidad.

La conferencia será presentada por un representante de la ciudad de Barcelona, anfitrión del evento, que dará una visión general de la electromovilidad en la ciudad.

- La agenda del evento contará con presentaciones detalladas de:
- La Hyper-Network de NeMo: Qué es y cómo funciona.
- The Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol
- Acceso a la Hyper-Network de NeMo y a las funciones comerciales del mercado de NeMo
- Seguimiento por una mesa redonda: “El futuro de la electromovilidad”

Además del programa de la conferencia, los participantes podrán visitar el área de exhibición donde se mostrarán diferentes aspectos de NeMo. Las demostraciones en vivo incluirán:

- NeMo, the BlockChain-based Hyper-Network
 - NeMo, la Hiper-Network basada en BlockChain
- The NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node
 - El mercado de NeMo y el nodo de ejecución
- Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure
 - Servidor neutral y estándar de Vehículo Extendido integrado con la infraestructura de NeMo
- End-to-end smart charging based on ISO 15118 and OCPP
 - Carga inteligente de extremo a extremo basada en ISO 15118 y OCPP
- NeMo Battery Services, Service creation in the Hyper-Network
 - Servicios de baterías NeMo, Creación de servicios en la Hiper-Red

Las demostraciones estarán acompañadas por una serie de posters técnicos.

El idioma de la conferencia es el inglés

Nos complace responder a sus consultas y concertar entrevistas para usted. Para todas las consultas, comuníquese con Hugo Roebroek, Gerente de Difusión de NeMo, a través del email h.roebroek@mail.ertico.com o llamando al +32 473 516 112.

Registro en el evento y actualizaciones: <https://www.eventbrite.com/e/from-projectto-market-seamless-electromobility-services-in-europe-registration-61996854260>

Para obtener más información, visite <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>

2.2 Inviting Stakeholders

An official invitation letter by **Dr. Angelos Amditis** (*NeMo Project Coordinator*) in pdf format was sent via email to NeMo stakeholders' mailing list as well as to partners' network and contacts. It is available online at project's website while a screenshot can be found in **Annex I**.

Additionally, a content template was circulated among the consortium members by **ERTICO** (*NeMo communication manager*) in order to assist the NeMo partners in inviting potential participants to the Final Conference and Exhibition via email.

2.2.1 Official invitation letter by the coordinator

Table 4: Content of the official invitation letter content by the coordinator

Official invitation letter by the coordinator

Dear Madam/dear Sir,

On behalf of the European Horizon 2020 project NeMo "Hyper-Network for Electromobility", I am very pleased to invite you to the project's Final Conference and Exhibition, organised in Barcelona, Spain, on Thursday, 19 September 2019. Concluding three years of research and development, the consortium will showcase how NeMo makes Electromobility in the road sector more attractive for businesses and users, during a one-day conference and exhibition. The NeMo Final Event and Exhibition aims to bring together industry and e-roaming platforms representatives, academics and researchers, road, charging point and grid operators, solution providers and other Electromobility stakeholders, to share its results leading to the node-based Hyper Network for Electromobility, the functionalities that it offers and its contribution towards seamless, interoperable and widely available services for all Electromobility actors.

Through a number of technical presentations, panel discussions, interactive demonstrations and hands-on sessions, prominent speakers from academia and industry as well as renowned experts in the field will present the key elements of the NeMo Hyper-Network. These elements include the NeMo Common Information Models, easy creation, execution and delivery of services on the Hyper-Network, as well as the smart horizontal services that NeMo has made available. In parallel, the Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol, which links different Electromobility roaming platforms and enables cross-provider Electromobility roaming seamlessly, will be on display; and the specific architecture developed for the Extended Vehicle and Neutral Server deployed via the project's OEMs, which assists the driver to experience improved services and access real vehicle data, will be presented to the attendees.

Join the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition to be among the first to learn about the project impacts on the Electromobility ecosystem and the partners' plans to continue the operation and development of NeMo's services through the establishment of an open association. Participants' interaction will be encouraged, during a panel discussion focusing on future needs for seamless Electromobility, while networking opportunities will be offered in the framework of the parallel exhibition.

Participation in the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition is free, but registration is mandatory to secure your place. To find out more and to register, please visit <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>.

For further questions, please contact info@nemo-emobility.eu

I look forward to welcoming you in Barcelona, on the 19th of September!

Yours faithfully,

Dr. Angelos Amditis

NeMo Project Coordinator Research Director,
Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece

2.2.2 Content template for email invitation

Table 5: Content template for email invitation to potential participants

Content template for email invitation to potential participants

Dear...,

On behalf of NeMo project – Hyper-Network for Electromobility – I am pleased to invite you **[and your colleagues / members of your association / etc. – edit as appropriate]** to the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition “From project to market: Seamless electromobility services in Europe”, in Barcelona on Thursday 19th September 2019.

This key event dealing with sustainable and interoperable electro-mobility is organised by ERTICO, the City of Barcelona and NeMo Coordinator ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems.

This one-day event concludes three years of work in this EU Horizon 2020 project, and will showcase how NeMo has contributed to making electromobility in the road sector more attractive, for both businesses and users. It will include technical presentations and a panel discussion, as well as the opportunity to experience the NeMo Hyper-Network functionalities in interactive demonstrations, exhibitions and hands-on sessions.

It is aimed at all sectors (public authorities, road operators, OEMs, other industry, research, service providers, developers and start-ups, mature students, etc.) with an interest in interoperable electromobility services, such as charging (including inter-operator roaming), smart EV navigation, brokerage, grid and battery related services. **[edit as appropriate to highlight the sector of the persons being invited]**

For more details and to download the agenda, please see <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>, which also links to the registration page.

Participation is free but registration is required via the above link.

We strongly recommend that interested participants book their place and also their hotel as soon as possible, as hotel availability is already limited at this period. A list of suggestions is available at the above website and on the registration page.

Please also see attached the official invitation letter from the Project Coordinator, Dr Angelos Amditis.

It would also be greatly appreciated if you could forward this message to colleagues and others in your wider network with an interest in electromobility, in particular through **[... Complete in case the addressee has a widely used network that can help us]**.

Best regards,

2.3 Inviting external speakers (panel discussion session)

A panel discussion session was organized by the consortium in order to further attract the attention of the participants during the event, and contribute with their knowledge and experience during the presentations and general discussions. For this reason, the well-established network of the consortium in the sector of electromobility was deployed for inviting prestigious external speakers. As the invitation was mainly based on personal contacts, there was no template required to follow.

2.4 Participant registration

The NeMo communication manager, ERTICO, created a space for the event at the **Eventbrite** where anyone interested to participate at the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition could be informed about the event (*date, time, agenda, venue locations*) and register by filling in the related fields in order to book a seat and participate at the event. All information collected were treated according to the principles in GDPR¹. The link where the NeMo event could be found at Eventbrite was the following one:

<https://www.eventbrite.com/o/nemo-project-20256208807>

Figure 1: NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition space at the Eventbrite

2.5 Venue Arrangements

2.5.1 Event hosting

The municipality of Barcelona made all the related actions for finding the proper venue to host the NeMo event. After examining several aspects, the decision was made for the building Ca l'Alier located in Poblenu neighbourhood, Carrer de Pere street, which can be easily accessed by public transportation. The building was a former factory which was recently renovated and operates as an **urban innovation centre**, with our event being one of the first events organized at the space. Two municipal electric cars were placed in front of the entrance during the event, while four charge points of the municipality of Barcelona are located outside of the Ca l'Alier building.

¹ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/EN/TXT/?uri=celex%3A32016R0679>

Figure 2: Ca l'Alier entrance with EVs placed outside

Moreover, catering services (*lunch, coffee breaks, etc.*) for the participants were foreseen and arranged by ERTICO in collaboration with the municipality of Barcelona.

2.5.2 Blueprint of the Conference Room

This blueprint depicts where the presentations and the panel discussions took place, where the stands with posters and demos were located.

Figure 3: Blueprint of the conference venue

2.5.3 Charge points at the venue

Charge points located outside of the Ca l'Alier building.

Figure 4: Charge points offered by Municipality of Barcelona (Ajuntament de Barcelona)

2.6 Promotional Materials

Promotional materials were used supplementary to all communication actions, and assisted in conveying the desired message. In our case, for the promotion of the event several types of promotional materials and giveaways (mementos) were created for either placing them at the conference room or distributing them to participants during the event. All communication materials had the project's branding on it, which included the logo of the project, the EU emblem and the project's number. The table below indicates numbers of items ordered for each promotional material / memento.

Most of the promotional materials that are presented within the current section were included in the attendee bag that was distributed to the participants at the beginning of the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition.

Table 6: Promotional material types and items ordered

Promotional Material / Memento	Items ordered	Designed and printed / ordered by:
Organic cotton bag	180 items	ERTICO
Cardboard eco touchscreen pen	250 items	ERTICO
Power bank solar charger 4000mAh	150 items	ERTICO
Wooden USB stick	150 items	ERTICO

NeMo Final Brochure	500 items	ERTICO
Conference Agenda	120 items	ERTICO (designed), Mosaic Factor (printed)
Posters	8 items	Mosaic Factor (printed)

Approximately 120 items per promotional material / memento were given out at the event to attendees, speakers, project partners, and staff and elected officials of the Ajuntament de Barcelona, who supported the event.

Finally, banners in digital format were created for the online promotion of the event.

2.6.1 Banners in digital format

Two versions of banner in digital format were created by ERTICO in order to assist the consortium in communicating and promoting the event via partners' websites and social media accounts. The scope of their creation was to raise the visibility of the event through all the available online channels and increase the number of participants.

Figure 5: “Register now!” banner long (digital format)

Figure 6: “Save the date!” banner (digital format)

Register now!

From project to market:
Seamless electromobility
services in Europe

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
Barcelona, 19th September 2019

www.nemo-emobility.eu/conference

Follow us on

Figure 7: “Register now!” banner square (digital format)

2.6.2 Advertising the event in social media

To attract further attention around the event the communication manager of NeMo, ERTICO, created pictures with quotes from the panellists regarding their vision on the future of electromobility that were posted on Twitter and LinkedIn accounts of the project and also shared in partners’ social media accounts.

Figure 8: Teaser with quote by Dr. Alexander Kröller for advertising the event via social media

NeMo contributes to simplifying the 'overall system and architecture' for electromobility, to reduce costs and to foster the emergence of an electromobility market of services.

Jean-Marc Rives
Chief Technical Officer, GIREVE
Speaker in the "Future of Electromobility" panel discussion

Join Jean-Marc and our other panellists at the NeMo Final Conference, 19 September at Ca l'Alfer, Barcelona

Last places available, registration closes on 10 September.
Register now (free): nemo-emobility.eu/conference

Event hosted by
Ajuntament de Barcelona

Figure 9: Teaser with quote from Jean-Marc Rives for advertising the event via social media posts

"NeMo boosts the interoperability of electromobility services"

Dr Evangelia Portouli
Senior Researcher, ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (Athens)
Speaker and panellist at the NeMo Final Conference, 19 September at Ca l'Alfer, Barcelona

Last day to register (free) **today**, 13 September
nemo-emobility.eu/conference

Event hosted by
Ajuntament de Barcelona

Figure 10: Teaser with quote by Dr. Evangelia Portouli for advertising the event via social media

2.6.3 Organic Cotton Bag

An eco-friendly fabric bag was created and distributed to the participants. The bag included event's promotional materials and mementos.

Figure 11: Fabric Bag

2.6.4 Brochure

The final project's brochure includes easy-to-read content for promoting the NeMo results and announcing the establishment of the BAEM.

Figure 12: Final Conference Brochure (inside)

Figure 13: Final Conference Brochure (outside)

2.6.5 NeMo Test Drive Flyer

In May 2019, 500 items of the NeMo Test Drive Flyer were printed for the ITS European Congress. Items in stock were included in the attendee bag that was distributed to all participants at the beginning of the event.

Figure 14: NeMo Test Drive Flyer

2.6.6 NeMo document holders

In October 2018, 200 items were printed for the NeMo Stakeholder Forum by ERTICO. Many items from that batch remained in stock so it was decided by the consortium to be handed out to the participants of the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition. The NeMo document holders were included in the attendee bag.

Figure 15: NeMo document holders

2.6.7 Cardboard eco touchscreen pen

An eco-friendly cardboard touchscreen pen was included also in the bag and was distributed to the participants.

Figure 16: Cardboard eco touchscreen pen

2.6.8 Wooden USB sticks

A wooden USB stick with the NeMo logo engraved was also included in the attendee bag.

Figure 17: Wooden USB sticks

2.6.9 Power bank solar charger

A power bank solar charger of 4000 mAh capacity was included in the bag and was also distributed to each participant.

Figure 18: Power bank solar charger

2.6.10 Roll-up banner

Figure 19: Roll-up banner (placed in Ca' l'Alier entrance)

2.6.11 Posters

Figure 20: Laminated poster placed in the exhibition area

3. Conference Day

The Final Conference and Exhibition of the NeMo project was held in Barcelona Spain on the 19th of September 2019. This one-day event included technical presentations and demonstrations of the produced NeMo results related to electromobility.

The conference began with the speech of Mr. Luís Gómez, Commissioner for Economic Promotion, Enterprise and Innovation from the city of Barcelona who welcomed the speakers, the panellists and the participants. Later on, Dr. Evangelia Portouli, senior researcher from ICCS, summarised NeMo's achievements during the three years of NeMo lifecycle.

After the opening speeches of the conference, the first session entitled "Creating a Hyper-Network for Electromobility" followed where partners analysed the results that they have produced.

In the final speech, Mr. Andrew Winder from ERTICO – ITS, explained how all the presented results during the first session will be utilised and exploited through the Business Alliance for Electromobility and effectively contribute to the electromobility sector. Also, new services will emerge by companies that will join the Hyper-Network, and thus it will make the journeys of EV drivers easier as they cross different EU countries. Mr. Winder closed his presentation by inviting all interested parties to state their interest and participate actively in this alliance in order to further promote the electromobility solution across Europe.

In the second session, entitled "Business and Technical Demonstrations of the NeMo Hyper-Network", partners highlighted the features of the NeMo Hyper-Network through technical demonstrations. Moreover, the participants had the opportunity to be informed by Mr. Thomas Walz from IBM Deutschland on how the NeMo marketplace will operate and how stakeholders can be involved in the Hyper-Network.

The final session included a panel discussion organised on the topic of the future of electromobility. The discussion was moderated by Dr. Evangelia Portouli and was held among representatives of prestigious companies who honoured us with their presence and active participation, and were asked to provide their view based upon their diverse backgrounds on what their future vision on electromobility is. The participants (panellists) in this discussion were:

- **Angel Lopez**, Ajuntament de Barcelona
- **Christian Hahn**, Hubject
- **Jean-Marc Rives**, Gireve
- **Jan Cupal**, VERBUND
- **Ichiro Sakai**, Honda
- **Alexander Kröller**, TomTom
- **Noshin Omar**, AVESTA Battery & Energy Engineering

Alongside the conference proceedings, the exhibition space was open and participants could be further informed through relevant posters and demos. In this context, Mr. Stephan Dengler and Mr. Volker Fricke, the winners of NeMo Hackathon from e3charge, presented "ChargeSharing: a community-based charging solution for EV drivers", as this was integrated in the Hyper-Network.

The project coordinator (ICCS) co-organized this event in close collaboration with ERTICO, the city of Barcelona and Mosaic Factor. The conference brought together 75 participants from small and medium-sized companies based mainly in Barcelona, representatives of consortia responsible for the implementation of European funded projects related with electromobility, as well as representatives of the municipality of Barcelona and ordinary citizens.

Figure 21: Panoramic view of the Conference Room

3.1 Agenda

The agenda of the event can be found as a screenshot at **Annex III**, while the content is provided at the table below.

Table 7: Agenda of the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition

Time	Item	Presenter
09:00-09:30	Registration / Coffee	
9:30-10:00	Conference opening session	
9:30	Welcome from the host and overview of Electromobility in the city of Barcelona	Senior representative from Ajuntament de Barcelona / City of Barcelona
9:40	Overview of NeMo achievements	Evangelia Portouli , ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
10:00-11:30	Conference session: Creating a Hyper-Network for Electromobility	
10:00	NeMo Hyper-Network, what it is and how it works	Thomas Walz , IBM Deutschland
10:15	Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol	Thomas Fousse , Gireve
10:35	NeMo Common Information Models	Christina Anagnostopoulou , ICCS
10:45	Easy Service Creation	Nils Mausch , Technical University of Berlin
10:50	Smart Horizontal services	Stefano Persi , Mosaic Factor

11:00	Evaluation activities and NeMo Impact <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NeMo test sites, the European Electromobility Test Drive and the NeMo Hackathon 	Christophe Moure , Applus+IDIADA
11:20	After NeMo: Building the Business Alliance for Electromobility	Andrew Winder , ERTICO – ITS Europe
11:30-11:50	Coffee Break / Exhibition visit	
11:50-13:00	Conference Session: Business and Technical demonstrations of the NeMo Hyper-Network	
11:50	Using the Hyper-Network: Access and business features of the NeMo Marketplace <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Partner on-boarding, Marketplace functionality 	Thomas Walz , IBM Deutschland
12:05	Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • NeMo Registration of an atomic or horizontal service. Service offering and contracting • Creation of a composite service: Charging point search based on mobility needs • Service execution, with focus on Integration bus and Translators • Demonstration of a use case: Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure 	Thomas Fousse , Gireve Nils Masuch , Technical University of Berlin Thodoris Theodoropoulos , ICCS Roberto Tola , CRF - Centro Ricerche Fiat
13:00-14:00	Lunch break / Exhibition visit	
14:00-15:30	Conference session: Panel discussion and conclusions	
14:00	Panel discussion: “The future of electromobility” <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Viewpoints and open discussion including representatives of different stakeholder types (public authority, electromobility roaming provider, energy sector, automotive sector, service providers) Moderated by Evangelia Portouli , ICCS	Àngel López , Ajuntament de Barcelona Christian Hahn , Hubject Jean-Marc Rives , Gireve Jan Cupal , VERBUND Ichiro Sakai , Honda Alexander Kröller , TomTom Noshin Omar , Avesta Battery & Energy Engineering
15:00	Conclusions	Evangelia Portouli , ICCS

15:30-
16:30

Networking drinks reception / Exhibition area remains open

The **exhibition area** will showcase different aspects of NeMo, including **technical posters** and the opportunity to talk to NeMo partners who will be giving the following **demonstrations**:

1. **NeMo the Blockchain based Hyper-Network: the NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node**, by IBM
2. **Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure**, by CRF
3. **Demonstration of Double Consent functionality to get User consensus for Neutral Server integration in the Extended Vehicle system**, by Honda R&D Europe
4. **Software for charge points enabling end-to-end communication for smart charging**, by BroadBit
5. **NeMo Battery Services**, by fka
6. **Service creation in the Hyper-Network**, by Technical University of Berlin
7. **ChargeSharing: a community-based charging solution for EV drivers**, by e3charge

3.2 Participation

The efforts made by the consortium during the preparation period of the event lead to the significant number of 75 participants who attended the event and took part in vivid discussions about the future of electromobility. Thirty (30) participants out of the total seventy-five (75) were external and the rest were members of the consortium or related to project partners. The external participants were representatives from the field of electric industry (mainly SMEs), policy makers, retailers, individuals and representatives from EU funded projects related to electromobility.

Figure 22: Participants at the exhibition area

Figure 23: Audience during the presentation sessions

3.3 Speakers

This chapter presents an **overview** of the sessions via photos taken (highlights) from the presentations that were made by the NeMo partners. A **detailed report** is provided in the **chapter 4** of the current document, while the speakers' original presentations (*derived from PowerPoint format*) are provided in **Annex V**.

3.3.1 Conference opening session

Figure 24: Luís Gómez in opening session (Welcoming participants)

Figure 25: Dr. Evangelia Portouli in opening session (Overview of NeMo achievements)

3.3.2 Creating a Hyper-Network for Electromobility session

Representative moments from the partners' presentations during the first session are provided here.

Figure 26: Thomas Walz presenting “NeMo Hyper-Network: What it is and how it works”

Figure 27: Christophe Moure presenting “Evaluation activities and NeMo impact”

Figure 28: Andrew Winder presenting “From NeMo to a Business Alliance for Electromobility”

3.3.3 Business and Technical demonstrations of the NeMo Hyper-Network session

Representative moments of the technical partners’ presentations of the second session are provided here.

Figure 29: Thomas Walz presenting “Using the Hyper-Network: Access and business features of the NeMo Marketplace”

Figure 30: Nils Masuch presenting “Creation of a composite service: Charging point search based on mobility needs”

Figure 31: Thodoris Theodoropoulos presenting “Service execution, with focus on Integration bus and Translators”

Figure 32: Technical Q&As – Speakers take the floor to answer the audience's queries

3.4 Panellists

In this chapter the experts in the field of electromobility (*panellists*), who took part in the panel discussion session are presented by providing their short bios. Moreover, photos taken from this session (*highlights*) are shown. A detailed report of the discussion is given in **chapter 4** of this deliverable.

3.4.1 Panellists short Bios

Dr. Evangelia Portouli

Senior Researcher - ICCS (Institute of Communication and Computer Systems), Greece

Dr. Evangelia Portouli holds a Mechanical Engineer degree with excellence from the National Technical University of Athens and a PhD on Cognitive ergonomics from the same Institute. She is a Senior Researcher and leader of the Administration, Quality and Dissemination of the I-SENSE Group of ICCS. In the period 1991-1994 she has worked in an industrial company, designing and developing prototype systems for vehicles. Since 1994 she has worked as research consultant on intelligent transportation systems. In the period 2005-2010 she has

worked as researcher in the Hellenic Institute of Transport of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas. Her scientific interests include the ergonomic design and development of driving automation and support systems.

Àngel López Rodríguez

Director of Electromobility strategy - City of Barcelona, Spain

PhD Angel López Rodríguez currently serves as Director of Barcelona's Electric Vehicle Program and Executive Director of the LIVE Platform, a public-private partnership that aims at promoting sustainable urban mobility in Barcelona. Prior to this, Mr. López served as Director for Mobility and Infrastructure at Barcelona City Council. In the past, he worked in major projects for the city councils of Madrid and Barcelona, the Catalanian regional government, the Spanish Directorate of Traffic (DGT) and the Spanish Ministry of Public Works, and had management responsibilities in private high-tech companies. His areas of expertise include traffic management, road safety and public transport systems. He holds a MSc and a PhD in civil engineering from Polytechnic University of Catalonia.

Christian Hahn

CEO - Hsubject GmbH, Germany

His career began at ThyssenKrupp and Daimler AG, followed by six years at PricewaterhouseCoopers in Berlin, where he specialized in consulting for the energy supply business. He began working on his first electric vehicle projects in 2008. He joined Hsubject in 2012, where he started as Head of Business Development and Administration and in 2015 Christian was appointed CEO of Hsubject GmbH. Following a change in the management team in January 2019, his primary focus is now on strategy, investor relations, and the global Hsubject company setup.

Jean-Marc Rives

Chief Technical Officer – GIREVE, France

Jean-Marc gained a long experience on IT and innovation projects at Renault company. At GIREVE, since 2013, he leads the technical part and the new services. He is also involved in several e-mobility-related research projects.

Ichiro Sakai

General Manager - Honda Motor Europe Ltd., Belgium

A graduate of Osaka Prefectural University with a master's degree in system engineering, Sakai joined Honda R&D Co., Ltd. in Japan in 1985. Since then, he has, among others worked in emission engineering and regulatory affairs in the USA and the EU. In 2018, he was appointed as the Japanese liaison engineer in Brussels where he works on regulatory issues in collaboration with stakeholders in an industry as well as in the EU institutions.

Alexander Kröller

Research Manager – TomTom, Germany

Alexander Kröller is leading TomTom's navigation research & innovation team, and responsible for collaborative research projects. He is also heading TomTom Lab, TomTom's company-wide innovation program. Before that, he pursued an academic career in algorithms.

Dr. Noshin Omar

CEO and Founder – ABEE (Avesta Battery & Energy Engineering), Belgium

Dr. Noshin Omar (*Male*) is the managing director of ABEE and has 14 years' experience in R&D projects. He obtained his PhD degree in electromechanical Engineering Sciences from the Vrije Universiteit Brussel in the field of Li-ion batteries for automotive applications. Since 2012 until March 2019, he was the Director of the Battery Innovation Centre at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel, where he was leading a team of 30 researchers in the field of energy storage. Over the last 14 years he has been active in various national and European projects in the field of characterisation, electrical, thermal, electrochemical and lifetime modelling of various rechargeable energy storage systems. He contributed to various European projects (*in total 25 projects*) such as SUPERLIB, BATTERIES2020, FIVEVB, ORCA, ASSURED, GHOST, OBELICS, IMAGE, SELFIE, ACHILLES, CEVolver, FITGEN, UPSCALE, ANABELLE, ENSEMBLE, VISION-xEV. He is very active in the field of European funded projects. He has more than 200 publications.

Jan Cupal

Senior Innovation Manager – VERBUND, Austria

Jan Cupal has been almost 12 years in VERBUND in Vienna, where he is Senior Innovation Manager in Business Development E-Mobility & Smart Grids, and was previously Senior Expert Corporate Development in VERBUND.

3.4.2 Panel Discussion Highlights

Figure 33: Dr. Evangelia Portouli presents the panellists and opens the panel discussion

Figure 34: Àngel López elaborates on his vision about the future of electromobility

Figure 35: Àngel López's equation

Figure 36: Dr. Evangelia Portouli coordinates the panel discussion

Figure 37: Christian Hahn elaborates on his vision about the future of electromobility

Figure 38: Jean-Marc Rives elaborates on his vision about the future of electromobility

Figure 39: Jan Cupal elaborates his vision about the future of electromobility

Figure 40: Ichiro Sakai elaborates on his vision about the future of electromobility

Figure 41: Alexander Kröller elaborates on his vision about the future of electromobility

Figure 42: Dr. Noshin Omar elaborates on his vision about the future of electromobility

3.5 Exhibition Area

The posters were placed in the exhibition area where participants had the opportunity to visit during the lunch and coffee breaks while it remained open and available throughout the whole duration of the event. There were 8 posters prepared by different partners (*ICCS, IBM, TU Berlin, ICOOR, IDIADA, Hubject, Gireve, BroadBit, Mosaic Factor, City of Barcelona*) and reviewed by ERTICO and the Steering Committee. Within the exhibition area videos of the NeMo project were displayed and live demonstrations were made.

Figure 43: Technical posters in the exhibition area

Figure 44: Display of the NeMo final video in the exhibition area

Figure 45: Demo by e3charge - Volker & Stephan (NeMo Hackathon winners)

Figure 46: Demo by BroadBit - Adam Knapp

3.5.1 Virtual Sensors for Electro-Mobility Services (Poster)

Virtual Sensors for Electro-Mobility Services

NeMo result theme:
Virtual sensors services for electromobility

Introduction: Why virtual sensors? Key partners involved

The need for deriving new data and introducing innovative services in the electromobility sector bring to the introduction of virtual sensors:

- Virtual Sensors (VSs) are introduced as **software sensors** that provide **indirect measurements of abstract conditions**, by **combining** sensed data from **heterogeneous physical sensors**
- A VS **logically reproduces** one or more **physical sensors** in the cloud platform, facilitating and increasing their functionalities, being capable of **performing complex tasks** that cannot be accomplished by physical sensors
- VSs are used in different fields of research such as energy, healthcare, mobility, etc., **to estimate or predict information/parameters** values from the distributed instrumentation measurements

Virtual Sensors implementation Methodology

VS implementation methodology based on three consecutive phases

- **1° Sensing phase:** gathering data from data providers and data sources (wired and wireless sensors)
- **2° Planning phase:** the collected data from external sources, together with the internal state of vehicle, are elaborated by internal algorithms to update the indirect measurement
- **3° Acting phase:** the last computation of the VS is requested from external users or other services, and the corresponding last updated output is delivered to them

Virtual sensors for electromobility

Personal Mobility Probability (PMP)

- The VS uses statistical algorithms and past trip history data to derive the driver most probable routes during the next calendar day with respective probabilities. Each route is a spatial-temporal path composed by the interpolation of Point Of Interest (POI).

Charge Price Prediction (CPP)

- The VS provide information about charge stations (latitude, longitude, tariff, power, distance, status), related to a specific time horizon (e.g. next 24 hours) and the area of interest of a given driver and predict charge session cost for the given driver selecting specific charge point

Tour Energy Demand (TED)

- The VS provides an estimation of the energy needed to make a journey from the destination to the arrival based on several information such as battery SoC, vehicle load, vehicle and driver historical consumption.

For further information
Maria Pia, Fanti
 • POLIBA (ICOOR)
 • mariapia.fanti@poliba.it
Michele, Roccotelli
 • POLIBA (ICOOR)
 • michele.roccotelli@poliba.it

Figure 47: Virtual Sensors for Electro-Mobility Services

3.5.2 IT Environment for Service Creation & Delivery in an Electromobility Business Network (Poster)

IT Environment for Service Creation & Delivery in an Electromobility Business Network

From project to market:
Seamless electromobility services in Europe
NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
Barcelona, 19th September 2019

Involved partners

1. The Challenges - IBM

- Development of **interoperable** and seamless electromobility services still a challenge
- Integration of services of **different stakeholders** still cumbersome due to missing interoperability and **discovery mechanisms**
- No **community-based** IT environment existent that enables the search, development and deployment of **value-added services** for the e-mobility domain
- Lack of **common information model** for all stakeholders;
- Stakeholders and business partners **not visible / transparent across Europe**
- Difficult to **establish collaboration and contracts** across Europe between stakeholders and business partners

2. NeMo Solution Approach IBM

The NeMo IT environment enables seamless integration of data and services for developers and business users.

NeMo provides a distributed environment to create, deliver and execute business services to all ecosystem partners connected in network.

3. NeMo Service Creation Environment TuB

- Provision of an **open-source** tool-suite, called Visual Service Design Tool - **VSDT**, which supports the developer in defining complex **e-mobility processes** with the help of standardized BPMN notation
- Comprehends a service finder interface in order to search and embed appropriate services within the **NeMo Open Cloud Marketplace** thanks to a semantic service description layer
- A **common information model** and appropriate data translators will enable **interoperability**
- Easy registration of services at the network via a **service description tool**
- Immediate deployment** of the developed processes to an execution component running in the NeMo Network

4. Service Delivery & Creation Marketplace (S&C)

NeMo Network September 2019

- S&C Marketplace – one stop shop for NeMo Services.
- S&C REST API – secured Service and Contract Registry API.
- Integration Bus – secure cross NeMo Node service invocation.
- BPMN Engine – create new NeMo services by orchestrating existing ones.
- DATA Translator – translate service specific data model to/from Common Information Mode, CIM.
- WALLET – store Hyperledger Fabric identities of the NeMo users.
- IBM Cloud Monitoring with Sysdig – operational visibility into the performance and health of the containerized NeMo components.
- Hyperledger Fabric – Enterprise grade permissioned distributed ledger platform.
- Docker Swarm Overlay Network – secured distributed network among NeMo Nodes.

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 713794

www.nemo-emobility.eu
@NeMo_electro

Figure 48: IT Environment for Service Creation & Delivery in an Electromobility Business Network (part A)

IT Environment for Service Creation & Delivery in an Electromobility Business Network

From project to market: Seamless electromobility services in Europe
 NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
 Barcelona, 19th September 2019

Thomas Walz, IBM, Germany, Thomas.Walz@de.ibm.com

Nils Masuch, DAI-Labor, TU Berlin, Germany, Nils.Masuch@dai-labor.de

5. NeMo Marketplace

6. Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure

7. Execution - TuB

- NeMo Service Execution mainly comprises two components:
- BPMN Runtime:** responsible for executing complex processes
 - Integration Bus:** provides the unified interface for all the services in the NeMo domain being the central component for executing intra-node and crossnode service-to-service calls.

8. Summary and Conclusions

- NeMo will provide:
- a **distributed service IT environment** where partner, service & contract information are stored in a decentralized manner using a **distributed ledger technology (HyperLedger, Blockchain)**
 - an IT environment, that lets developer **search & use third party services**
 - a BPMN-based tool-suite, that provides the possibility to **specify value-added E-Mobility IT services**
 - an IT **deployment/delivery mechanism** that lets business users easily take part in the NeMo Open Marketplace
 - a **common information model** to unify the business objects for all electro-Mobility services
 - increased innovation towards **Digital Single Market for Europe**

Figure 49: IT Environment for Service Creation & Delivery in an Electromobility Business Network (part B)

3.5.3 Booking Services (Poster)

Figure 50: Booking Services

3.5.4 Grid Services (Poster)

Grid Services

WPS Electromobility actor
Services
Task 5.2 Grid related services

Grid Services: An added value service layer for NeMo
ICCS-ICOOR

A portfolio of services targeting a diverse set of requirements targeting driver experience and grid constraints

- Layer of services using data available in the hypernetwork through NeMo's execution layer
- Data integrated by various components through the CIM (Common Information Model)

- Load management services providing feasible charging points according to daily demand profiles along a given route from origin to destination
- Load forecasting due to EV charging; providing forecasts of the charge load for a given station or in a specific area based on historical data.

Service portfolio, methodology and invocation

Services available through NeMo's interoperable REST API, through input-output objects following the CIM (Common Information Model):

Implementation based on the microservices paradigm enabling scalability, redundancy and rapid deployment through containerization

Retrieve a charging profile optimized according to daily demand profiles along a given route from origin to destination

Retrieve list of charging point along a given route from origin to destination

Provides load forecast due to EV charging for a given station by a CPO

Provides load forecast due to EV charging in a specific area by the operating CPO/CPOs

Conclusions

Creating grid services in NeMo → The CIM enables the semantic description of a large portion of grid related electromobility data objects (Charging profiles,)

Invoking grid services → CIM eases invocation of grid service by providing ready to use data object. Integration bus interface simplifies invocation of services

Grid services → Support the stability of grid, enable integration of electro mobility with the power system, can be used to shape grid friendly attitudes by EV drivers

Marketplace; an enabler of added values services

- ✓ Index of services ready to be integrated by added value services
- ✓ Contracting mechanism
- ✓ Extended service information required for rapid prototyping
- ✓ Integration of smart services

For further information

<p>Thodoris Theodoropoulos</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICCS thodoris.theodoropoulos@iccs.gr 	<p>Dr. Michele Roccotelli</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ICOOR michele.roccotelli@poliba.it
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 @NeMo_electro
www.nemo-emobility.eu

Figure 51: Grid Services

3.5.5 Common Information Models (Poster)

Common Information Models (CIM)

WP3 NeMo Data Management
Task 3.5 Common Information Models

NeMo's Interoperability layer

ICCS

Tackled the lack of standards for electromobility data exchange and service provision.

- **Common Information Models:** protocol to describe electromobility data in a structured and normalised way

- Dynamic translation of data and services interfaces according to the needs of involved stakeholders to support interoperability
- Essential data, that are scattered across actors, become available in a common and consistent format

CIM deployment and implementation

CIM covers electromobility operations by describing relevant Objects (physical objects and data structures) related to :

- Electric Vehicle
- Smart grid
- Marketplace
- E-Roaming
- User business objects
- EV charging infrastructure business objects – Charge Session

The template of the eM3 Electric Vehicle ICT Interface Specifications Part 2: Business Objects V1.0 was used to describe the business objects

CIM Implementation via Data Translators

Attributes per Object: Name, Definition, Necessity, Number of Instances, Format

CIM usage

During Service creation → translation transformation logic generation (PSM-CIM mapping, semantic annotation, service registration)

During Service invocation → dynamic service search, request/response messages, service execution

Conclusions and next steps

Benefits of NeMo CIM

- ✓ Enables easy information exchange among all involved actors
- ✓ New services generate and exchange data according to the CIM
- ✓ Data translators enable the translation of data to the NeMo CIM
- ✓ Integration of smart services

Continuous CIM update:

Liaison with standardization groups (eM3)
CIM versioning (BAEM)

For further information

Evangelia Portouli

- ICCS
- v.portouli@iccs.gr

Christina Anagnostopoulou

- ICCS
- christina.anagnostopoulou@iccs.gr

Figure 52: Common Information Models (CIM)

3.5.6 Pan-European Inter-roaming for Electromobility (Poster)

**Pan-European Interroaming
for Electromobility**

From project to market:
Seamless electromobility
services in Europe

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
Barcelona, 19th September 2019

EROAMING FOR ELECTROMOBILITY

HUBJECT

FROM EROAMING TO INTERROAMING

NeMo Inter-roaming Model

The Inter-roaming Protocol is a functional protocol that:

- describes all necessary services and interfaces to assure the interconnection between an eRoaming platform and the NeMo Hyper-Network (exposure of eRoaming features to NeMo)
- provides a technical and business framework for the interaction between two or more eRoaming Platforms

NeMo INTERROAMING IMPLEMENTATION via GIREVE and HUBJECT

INTERROAMING PROCESSES as NeMo services

- Exchange of Charging Station Data
- Cross platform Authorisation
- Exchange of Charge Detail Records

USER EXPERIENCE

EV Driver can charge seamlessly using the charging network of the different eRoaming Platforms

Project Coordinator
Dr. Angelos Amditis
Institute of Communication
and Computer Systems
a.amditis@iccs.gr

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Figure 53: Pan-European Inter-roaming for Electromobility

3.5.7 V2G Wireless Authentication Solution and Test Framework for Smart Charging (Poster)

V2G Wireless Authentication Solution and Test Framework for Smart Charging

NeMo result theme:
Electromobility actors services
Integration and Validation

Overview

- New draft version of ISO 15118 introduces authentication over WLAN
- Wireless authentication is a novel method for EV authentication
- Challenges in wireless case: association, authentication and authorization
- EV association is a trivial task, if the charging cable is already connected

Wireless Authentication Solution (WAS) and TTCN-3 based test framework have been developed

Key partners involved

Activities

Development of WAS capable SECC

- Prototypical implementation of parts of the ISO 15118-2 2nd edition / ISO 15118-8
- Focusing on certificate based authentication
- Runs on embedded system environment

Test framework

- ISO 15118-4 contains conformance test cases for wired charging
- Testing and Test Control Notation version 3 (TTCN-3) based test scripts have been customized

Association and pairing sequence

EV – Electric Vehicle
EVCC – Electric Vehicle Communication Controller
EVSE – Electric Vehicle Supply Equipment
SECC – Supply Equipment Communication Controller

Key results

WAS uses standardized messages

- Seamless authentication without driver actions
- Standard for international authentication interoperability

WAS is validated by the independently developed test framework

Test framework

Web user interface

For further information

Ádám Knapp
BroadBit
adam.knapp@broadbit.net

Nadim El Sayed
Technische Universität Berlin
nadim.elsayed@dai-labor.de

Figure 54: V2G Wireless Authentication Solution and Test Framework for Smart Charging

3.5.8 NeMo: the Block Chain based Hyper-Network. The NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node: What it is and how it works (Demo)

A live demonstration of the NeMo Hyper-Network functionalities and of the Node network operation followed. The demo showcased the available NeMo partner and user roles with respective access control, as well as the features available from business perspective. In particular, it was demonstrated how a service consumer or service provider, can access a NeMo Node, how he/she finds and contracts a service and how to register a service and create the corresponding service offering via the NeMo Marketplace.

IBM, Technical University of Berlin, ICCS - Contact: Thomas.Walz@de.ibm.com

3.5.9 Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo Hyper-Network (Demo)

A specific architecture for an Extended Vehicle and Neutral Server developed by NeMo, following the relevant work by ACEA (*the European Automobile Manufacturers Association*) and ISO was presented. It was deployed by 3 OEMs, the two project partners CRF (*Centro Ricerche Fiat*) and Renault, and NeMo Associate Partner, Honda. A key aspect is that the driver consents twice to sharing data from the electric vehicle with an external 3rd service provider through the Neutral Server and the NeMo Hyper-Network. In this way, the driver experiences improved services, as the service provider has access to real-time vehicle data.

CRF, IBM, TomTom, Renault - Contact: roberto.tola@crf.it

3.5.10 Demonstration of Double Consent functionality to get User consensus for Data Provision (Demo)

An important aspect in the Extended Vehicle standard, the Neutral Server concept and the NeMo Hyper-Network is the availability of vehicle data for the 3rd party service provider. Therefore, the driver must

have the choice to decide with whom he or she wants to share this data. This demonstration showed how a driver can selectively share her or his vehicle data using the “Double Consent” concept in a very comfortable and transparent way; and also how 3rd party providers can make use of this concept for service provision.

Honda R&D Europe - Contact: Marc.Bechler@de.hrdeu.com

3.5.11 Service Creation (Demo)

The creation of a composite service was demonstrated, that enables searching for charging points based on mobility needs.

Technical University of Berlin (DAI-Labor), fka, Politecnico di Bari - Contact: Nils.Masuch@dai-labor.de

3.5.12 NeMo Battery Services (Demo)

The simulated battery services as developed in the project were presented. (The simulator device is provided as reference in the picture below, though it was not used during the final event due to logistic complications).

fka GmbH - Contact: joerg.kuefen@fka.de

3.5.13 Software for charge points enabling end-to-end communication for smart charging

The solution demonstrates end-to-end communication through the EV – Recharging station – Central System entities providing smart charging features, like plug-and-charge, scheduled recharging, authentication, power balancing, rate negotiation etc. The key contribution is the software component developed for charge points that seamlessly integrates the ISO 15118 protocol and the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP). It can be considered as the “last mile” of NeMo Hyper-Network up to the vehicles. The demo reflects predefined use cases of the project related to smart charging.

BroadBit - Contact: adam.knapp@broadbit.net

3.5.14 ChargeSharing solution integrated into the NeMo Hyper-Network (NeMo Hackathon winner)

ChargeSharing from e3charge is a community-based network of private electric charging station providers. It allows owners of private charge points to rent out their charge points to others, without the user needing to create a new subscription or download a new app, but instead using standard well-known

payment providers. The technical solution enables data on such charge points to be published in various charging station directories (online mapping) as well as in-vehicle navigation systems. This application was awarded the winning service of the NeMo hackathon, and e3charge was invited to the Final Conference and Exhibition to demonstrate the service and how it has been integrated into the Hyper-Network.

e3charge - Contact: info@e3charge.net

4. Report of Discussions

This section constitutes a detailed report on presentations and discussions (*including the content of Q&As sessions*) that were made throughout the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition. For achieving the best outcome and also ensure that the reader would acquire – as much as possible - the same information and knowledge that participants of the event gained through their physical presence, a mixture of practices was used. Thus, a pro-forma template (*see Annex IV*) for the proceedings of the conference was created for assisting the organising team of NeMo Conference to take notes on the spot during the event.

In addition, the original presentations (*retrieved from PowerPoint format*) of each speaker are provided in **Annex V**. For reader's ease, the current section presents the core messages (*summaries*) per presentation. The combination of the aforementioned practices (*notes via pro-forma templates, original PowerPoint speakers' presentations and summaries*) allows to the reader to have a complete view and understanding from the day of NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition.

4.1 Opening Session

4.1.1 Welcome from the host and overview of Electromobility in the City of Barcelona, Luís Gómez

The representative of BCN, Luís Gómez. Commissioner for Economic Promotion, Enterprise and Innovation | City of Barcelona | Barcelona Spain.

Mr. Gómez, being involved in economic promotion of BCN, pointed out that the cities need to change their mobility schemes, and transform the mobility for improving the quality of city life, and, as a consequence, transforming the industry. USA, China, and Japan are innovating and adding very fast value and money to be the first to change the mobility. EU cannot stay back to these leading countries. EU needs to be a reference and cities should play an important role in that. The Municipality of Barcelona city, for example, receives delegations from other countries visiting to see the city's activities regarding mobility, autonomous mobility, etc., modelling how to build cities with high quality of life. BCN, having its first charging point installed in 2009, is open and expresses the need to work looking at the people needs together with small companies as well as industries to change the mobility. More cities need to be involved in such projects like NeMo. Watching the developments in Asia, we need to provide something more.

4.1.2 Overview of NeMo achievements, Dr. Evangelia Portouli (ICCS)

Dr. Evangelia Portouli opened the sessions giving special thanks to BCN, for hosting the Final Event and for their participation within the project. Mobility changes and electromobility is a part of it and contributes to this change. The presentation over the general overview and achievements of the project followed by Dr. Portouli. Also, Mr. Volker Fricke, the NeMo hackathon winner, was introduced as an exhibition participant showcasing his offered service.

4.2 Creating a Hyper-Network for Electromobility

4.2.1 NeMo Hyper-Network: What it is and how it works, Thomas Walz (IBM Germany)

The opening presentation of the session, introduced the main IT challenges that were addressed in the technical development within NeMo based upon which the main architecture principles were formed. The Hyper-Network was developed based on a distributed hyperledger framework upon blockchain applications, with open APIs and Identity and Access management in order to secure applications and services. The integration of business partners and their services provision are done via the NeMo Nodes, that can interact and make service-to-service calls via the integration bus and share the same service registry by the marketplace data replication across the node network. The single Node architecture was explained, and the current status of the Hyper-Network business partners and registered services was presented. A use case based upon the itinerary planning service developed within NeMo to share in-vehicle data to third party service providers, like the navigation service provider, using the NeMo Neutral server and the Extended Vehicle standard, which was demonstrated in ACEA working group, was showcased as this was implemented by 3 OEMs and complied with the NeMo Common Information Models.

4.2.2 Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol, Thomas Fousse (GIREVE)

The presentation begun with explaining the necessary communication flow that takes place between EMSPs and CPOs so that a customer of an EMSP can charge at the CPOs charge point. The lack of interoperability in the explained access topologies was creating complexity and reducing overall efficiency. The needed integration of existing solutions came as a result of the project with the development of the Inter-Roaming protocol that enables the connection of the 2 eRoaming platforms within the project and their exposure to the Hyper-Network, and increased the accessible charging points. Now a customer of an EMSP that is connected to the first platform can enable charging at a CPO who is a customer of the second platform seamlessly. The technical process was standardized via the NeMo Common Information Models and the open interfaces, allowing for new services creation and deployment features. The business model to support these connections is also proposed within the project in order to define the contractual terms of the business agreements among the involved actors and will be the task of the future BAEM.

4.2.3 NeMo Common Information Models, Christina Anagnostopoulou (ICCS)

The need for a harmonised data management domain within NeMo was recognized from the beginning, coming to address the challenges of lack of interoperability in electromobility services, the need for common data and information modelling, the lack of standardisation in services provision and the diversity of electromobility actors. The NeMo Common Information Model (CIM) provides models for all the physical objects and data structures relevant to the use cases of the project, based upon existing information modelling and data exchange standards in order to make data available to the correct actors in a consistent format. The agents called Data Translators are enabling the translation of existing services to the NeMo CIM and their publication to the Hyper-Network. The business objects were categorized in 8 logical categories, with defined attributes per object and based upon the template of the eMI3 specifications. The objects for the Electric Vehicle, the Smart Charging functionalities, the Charge Session, the Marketplace, the EV user, the eMobility Report, the Charging Infrastructure, the Vehicle preparation were presented and examples were given. CIM implementation supports the processes of service creation and invocation that allow for the dynamic translation from proprietary models to CIM and

vice versa. Concluding, CIM support the standardization and interoperability in electromobility services and allow for integration of new smart services. The models are open and shared and will be updated as needed by the BAEM.

4.2.4 Easy service Creation, Nils Masuch (Technical University of Berlin)

The service creation domain supports the integration of existing services into the NeMo Hyper-Network, as well as the creation of composite services that include combining services that reside in the Nodes of different business partners of the Hyper-Network. Within this domain a toolchain is provided in order to search and find appropriate services, compose the found ones, test the final composition and describe the final service semantically in CIM, and lastly deploy it in the NeMo service registry.

4.2.5 Smart Electromobility Services, Stefano Persi (Mosaic Factor)

Within the Hyper-Network, the B2B marketplace allows the provision of added-on functionality usable in the whole environment, connecting all electromobility actors, supporting the seamless interoperability of B2B and B2C services. Service providers can provide existing and new services, publish easily, combine other services for creation of smart added value services, and get a better knowledge of the users. The electromobility users can access global level services via a single easily accessible marketplace, combine different services and enjoy eRoaming interoperability. Services available in the Hyper-Network can support daily commute needs as well as occasional trips, for example CP prediction service or Service Brokerage can optimize selection and services upon criteria and personal mobility needs, etc., and a hands-on example was provided upon the use cases of the project.

4.2.6 Evaluation activities and NeMo impact, Christophe Moure (Applus IDIADA)

The presentation focused on the validation activities of the Hyper-Network, based upon the test sites and the European Electromobility Test Drive, as well as the NeMo Hachathon, organized in March 2019, in order to engage external organizations into the usage of the NeMo open tools and evaluate their effectiveness. The winner of the Hackathon was announced according to the criteria set, to be the Charge Sharing solution, allowing CPOs to rent their charging network, developed by e3charge. The 5 test sites and their scenarios, the services involved in each and the outcomes of the analyses, were also presented in detail. The second European test drive of the project resulted in a significant improvement of the driver satisfaction thanks to the implementation of the Hyper-Network and the Inter-Roaming protocol.

4.2.7 From NeMo to a Business Alliance for Electromobility, Andrew Winder (ERTICO – ITS Europe)

NeMo project developments will be continued and supported via the founding of the Business Alliance for Electromobility (BAEM) that will build a self-sustaining business model for a solid future of the Hyper-Network. The vision is to promote interoperability of electromobility services via participation in standardization processes and act as a central operation hub in Europe for all electromobility actors, offering intelligence and added value via a unique marketplace. This Alliance will be founded as a not-for-profit association, open to all relevant stakeholders, building a B2B network to facilitate making business and ensuring the exploitation of the project's results. The value proposition and the key activities of BAEM were also presented, while it was explained that the revenue model will be based upon subscription fee for the business members. Open invitation was made to all participants that can further state their interest via the project's web portal.

4.3 Business and Technical demonstrations of the NeMo Hyper-Network

4.3.1 Using the Hyper Network: Access and business features of the NeMo marketplace, Thomas Walz (IBM Germany) – *Business Demonstration*

This session presented hands-on the main architecture of the NeMo Node and the Hyper-Network with its current deployment with the Nodes of the partners, explaining the different types and user roles. A business partner can join the Hyper-Network with his own Node or as an affiliated of existing Node, being able to use the Node components and the offered functionality, have credentials to login and navigate the marketplace, where important information about partners' profiles and services can be found, search, register, offer and contract a specific service of interest. Insights to the marketplace and the provided information was given. Tools are also provided for constant monitoring of the nodes network.

4.3.2 Registration of an atomic or horizontal service. Service offering and contracting, Thomas Fousse (GIREVE) – *Technical Demonstration*

From the perspective of a service provider, the project partner Gireve having joined the marketplace to offer their services to the whole ecosystem, presented the experience to publish services in the Hyper-Network and offer them commercially, by providing a step by step overview of the process. The existing service, that resides in Gireve's IT environment, is being semantically annotated via CIM and service creation tools, the transformation logic is provided via the mapping of the proprietary Gireve protocol to the NeMo CIM, the end point of the service is described, and all this information is registered at the business object of a NeMo service under the business profile of the company. The service now will appear at the company's services list and can also be offered via a service offering that when selected can be invoked based upon the already registered transformation logic.

4.3.3 Creation of a composite service: Charging point search based on mobility needs, Nils Masuch (TUB) – *Technical Demonstration*

In this phase, the open service creation tools were presented in detail, explaining the components this domain consists of as well as their position within a NeMo Node. The participants got a view of the Eclipse tool that is used as the visual representation tool of the composite service creation suite with the BPMN editor incorporated, and how this can be used, services found and combined and finalised, was presented via a relevant use case example. The deployment and testing functionality are the final steps of this process. The service modelling is based upon the NeMo CIM, the Web Ontology Language format (OWL-s) for the semantic descriptions with an editor for defining relevant parameters and restrictive specifications. Then any provider is ready to register the resulted service at the marketplace as previously described.

4.3.4 Service execution, with focus on Integration bus and Translators, Thodoris Theodoropoulos (ICCS) – *Technical Demonstration*

The example follows the step of service invocation, either for an atomic or composite service, upon the NeMo-wide execution system architecture, the integration bus, thus allowing for service-to-service invocation by the respective nodes both on the consumer and provider sides. The relevant API that is involved in this process and promotes interoperability in the system was also presented. The security aspect is equally important and the appropriate access control is realized via the Identity Access Management. The processes for service look-up, dynamic service translation before execution, and

finally service invocation – for composite service invocations also, where multiple internal invocations are involved – were explained in detail.

4.3.5 Demonstration of a use case: Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure, Roberto Tola (CRF) – Technical Demonstration

Summing up the technical demonstration session, was the presentation of the project use case upon the architecture developed for secured sharing of in-vehicle data to any third-party service providers by the consent of the EV driver, enabling added value service provision to the end user. The integration of the OEMs backend was realized via the Neutral Server and the Extended Vehicle standard, fulfilling the EU guiding principles and the data privacy via the double consent approach. This was demonstrated at the Italian test site as well as to ACEA working groups, including implementation of NeMo proposed architecture by CRF, Renault and Honda. In the Italian test site, a Courtesy Assistant app as well as Navigation service provider were requesting information from the vehicle to allow for CP booking, alert about the battery low level and CP rebooking upon the monitoring of the vehicle status and the road information.

4.3.6 Q & As in Technical Demonstrations

The following table presents in an easy to read manner the questions made by the audience (addressed to the speakers) at the end of the technical demonstration session. Moreover, it provides to the reader the answers that speakers gave on the respective queries.

Table 8: Q & As in Technical Demonstration Session

Q&As in Technical Demonstration Session	
Q&A No. 1	<p><u>Question:</u> Mrs. Judit Bataye (Mobility Innovation Consultant SIX-TER / Ouishare)</p> <p><i>“There are several car sharing services and companies in BCN, extra to the municipality activities, and they are not in the project, how they can get connected? All these other existing initiatives in BCN can be linked and how?”</i></p> <hr/> <p><u>Answer:</u> Dr. Evangelia Portouli (ICCS) explained that everything is open and the BAEM that will be taking over the Hyper-Network, invites all parties to join, and these initiatives will also be able to connect and join the Hyper-Network, starting by stating their interest to participate to NeMo. So, all companies and initiatives can join and get linked to the Hyper-Network as well as to each other. BCN is a partner as a municipality, but also offers services and is connecting with service providers.</p>
Q&A No.2	<p><u>Question:</u> <i>“Is it able to retrieve the SoC and SOH of the battery to provide that to the right actors?”</i></p> <hr/> <p><u>Answer:</u> Küfen, Jörg (FKA) explained that this is relevant, the vehicle interface is able to do that, but the data openness and reliability is an issue on the supply chain, since it is complicated to provide live info. The Extended Vehicle standard described the interfaces, and</p>

the concept is involving with behaviour diagnostics – being regulated and e-mobility. CIM defines some of the values, and the more use cases the more the defined parameters will be.

A public interface (Trustee Server) is provided in NeMo to get access to the vehicle data, not at the extend that we may need today but initially it is provisioned and it can be further extended. (Jörg Küfen, Thomas Walz, Roberto Tola)

Roberto Tola mentioned the ACEA demo, where a real use case was demonstrated, facing successfully the problem of in-vehicle data provision to several third parties, after the EV user consent.

Q&A No.3

Question: **Mr. Julio Cesar Diaz Cabrera,**

(Research, ITE - Instituto Tecnológico de la Energía),

“Is the architecture open to produce new variables to the user behaviour vs the forecasting of the SoC?”

Answer: **Dr. Evangelia Portouli (ICCS)** said that the engagement of more companies will result in providing a variety of parameters that can be used – i.e. weather prediction/modelling companies, traffic information companies, etc. - to support the precondition of the car upon the forecast on the SoC. The backbone is ready via CIM and we are welcoming these actors to update the protocols and include these data sets in the future, we are open and everyone is welcome.

4.4 Panel Discussion and Conclusions

4.4.1 Dr. Evangelia Portouli, ICCS

Opening the panel session, Dr. Portouli introduced the panellists as well as the topic of discussion and asked them to present to the audience their views on how electromobility will change the future and be integrated in the everyday life. The discussion about our expectations on the future started with insights by each panellist, as described below.

4.4.2 Àngel López, Barcelona Regional

Mr. Lopez provided an overview of past, present and future of mobility from the cities perspective, and pointed out that the key issues still evolves around providing appropriate parking space for a city. An equation presented as a way to track the respective needs of the different eras. In the past, for example, we needed mobility and a place to park. Presently, pollution shifts the game to the plug level. We need a place to plug, a place to park and plug, and a plug to charge. Shared connected automated services is the prospect mobility future, shifting the mobility need to sharing, thus increasing complexity, and now adding to the equation not only space but also energy. For electromobility success, people acceptance is needed. NeMo project is the B2B project that worked in the technical complexity, mobility and accessibility, while the need now is for all to look ways for people acceptance.

4.4.3 Christian Hahn, Hubeject

Mr. Hahn, started stating that EV charging needs to be as easy as possible, as seamless as possible. This of course needs market collaboration. Gireve and Hubeject demonstrated collaboration within the

project, but other players in local level, need also to collaborate. The topic of security, handling customer data and the need to do it properly, when still today most of RFID cards are not very secure, comes next. It is necessary to trust each other in security level, having clear guidance and regulation, again jointly.

End customer experience is the next focus point. Once the customer understands that the EV is better to use, then the customer will make the shift. Lots of associations analysed the customer experience, and still drivers are facing issues when charging, when starting charging sessions, it is not clear who to call once something is not working, etc. Added value becomes the last focus point. Integration of EVs to the grid system is an innovative service and such services need to be broadly available.

A study in the US about their EV perception resulted that 4/10 believe that EVs still need petrol. Educating people to understand the value of EVs and that they are better is essential. Businesses need also to stand up for specific activities, supporting sustainable processes in order to survive. This is absolutely essential to their success.

4.4.4 Jean-Marc Rives, Gireve

Mr. Rives highlighted that we are in fact, in front of a big change in volume, while today electromobility is considered small, the forecast is a higher growth of numbers. The reasons why people will choose to use an EV, are not based on green mobility or reduction of CO2 emissions, but on the offered experience, because it will be fun, cool, pleasant, and convenient. Thus, it is essential to be giving to the EV driver the means to have this type of experience. The vehicle now is quite good with relevant OEM investment, but charging still remains a bit complex, and the ecosystem is also staying behind.

EV charging needs reduced complexity in order to support the increase of the pleasure that an EV offers. We are certain to arrive in high numbers of EVs usage, and such a mass market needs to face the security issues that rise. Even yet the health safety issues, ensuring payments or using a CP without e-shock, etc. Although today mainly it is about IT security that further needs improvement, the whole security domain needs to be dealt with. It is important to increase the power of infrastructure and enlarge the number of services and the different solutions provided. Mass markets need a clear market model, and still in electromobility there is confusion in actors, playing several roles.

Secondly, electromobility is only a part of mobility. Car sharing, autonomous vehicles, new user behaviour regarding vehicles and mobility points out the need to improve the level of services quality for a seamless experience in the whole mobility domain, via openly merging the electromobility with the rest of mobility ecosystem.

Third, let's not forget about energy: smart grids, smart cities, smart charge. Here also new smart services need to be available to allow for a connected energy domain and the uptake of the cross-benefits from the mobility domain.

Concluding, facing a mass market the progress in reducing complexity on data exchange, algorithms and IT, interconnected systems, real time info exchange (IT), etc., and compliance needs must be addressed, new services offered and a market structure clearly defined.

4.4.5 Jan Cupal, VERBUND

Coming from energy, Mr. Cupal, explained how Verbund, the Austrian energy actor, has a long history celebrating even its 70th birthday this year, so based upon their past experience they can look into the future, not in the sense of what will immediately happen tomorrow. An increase of electromobility by 30-40% is expected, placing us at the beginning of the shift from oil gas value chain to the electromobility value chain. The oil industry is very strong, when something disrupts this group, they react in panic although they have built-in buffers.

In electromobility, we have to electrify millions of vehicles. By 2040, 5 million passenger EV cars are estimated to be on the road. The energy players need to provide the amount of power and deliver it in REAL time (vs the oil market), via the DSO and transmission grid flow of power. The challenge lies in this key word: collaboration of all business partners involved, which is now missing as well as the framework to support that.

NeMo provided a first step towards that collaboration. In eRoaming we already saw an immediate benefit, for charging processes we need to also build the chain of collaboration. No energy player is prepared to do that. In NeMo, partners managed to test a use case towards this framework, of how these collaborations could work. But a lot of effort is needed.

4.4.6 Ichiro Sakai, Honda

In 2019, Honda became a member of ACEA, to fulfil the need to incorporate other than their usual strong engineering structure. Mr. Sakai expressed how he has mainly lived in the ICE era, having experienced the EVs only in a testing environment, thus he is excited for the EV future although there is a struggle in front of us. In Frankfurt, recently Honda announced the Honda-e mass production with a small 35 kWh battery with driving range more than 200km. Honda also proposes an Integrated concept for a carbon free society using electromobility. Solutions supporting that approach are a Honda power charger and charging management-bidirectional features to satisfy demand and supply. Charging also within the city can be facilitated by connecting the smart cable provided by Honda atop a bulb or conventional CP and a smart meter with a set tariff.

Power management for charging at home is also essential. EVs should have a significant role and responsibility for a carbon free society. Batteries range and affordability is also a topic needing further effort. Connectivity to the network of actors is a key element also, made possible via NeMo.

4.4.7 Alexander Kröller, TomTom

Mr. Kröller expressed his vision on the electromobility of the future. He envisioned an EV user that in the future would feel sorry for those who will still use an ICE vehicle, as these technologies will become increasingly troublesome to use, forbidden in controlled pollution zones, etc., making more difficult to have an ICE car in the future. EV numbers are already growing. But still this reflects a tiny portion of today's vehicles. The bad news is that we have to make things easier. Make easy for business customers to create services. EV charging services, routing optimization will allow for easy integration and easy usage by humans. Everything has not reached a level of completeness yet, thus the need to collaborate becomes stronger.

4.4.8 Dr. Noshin Omar, AVESTA

Of course we need to agree with the necessity of the public acceptance, and the security enforcement, Dr. Omar stated. EVs need to be first affordable, then sustainable from energy perspective. Electromobility fleet is now 2-3%. One of the challenges is energy storage. Battery accounts for about 40-50% of the cost of the vehicle. Battery manufacturing is presently mainly made in Japan, Korea, China and mostly not from green electricity. Solutions need to be sustainable and factory capacity increased. By 2030, batteries will have to provide double range extension at the same volume. If energy is doubled, the cost of the vehicle can be reduced by 50%.

Once the million numbers of EVs are plugged and charging at 30-100kWh, they can become sources of explosion, if something goes wrong, if the design is not appropriate or real time monitoring systems are not available. One strategy, for example, is based on doubling of electric range targeting further public

acceptance. Safe and sustainable solutions are needed, where the choice of charging based on green energy or not is available. Battery manufacturing needs to work towards improving affordability.

4.4.9 Dr. Evangelia Portouli, ICCS

Concluding the session, Dr. Portouli, gathered the key points of the discussion: the needed collaboration, energy management, security, easiness and seamless experience, battery manufacturing, smart and fun services offer. It was highlighted how energy must be produced at the time that is needed thus energy management is essential, along with charging scheduling so that the network is not overloaded. The question was raised, if we can really consider the possibility for energy to flow out of my battery to the grid. The relevant discussion is presented in the next session.

Dr. Portouli after the overall discussion thanked everyone for their participation and pointed out how NeMo has indeed achieved a small or bigger step upon the needed effort towards collaboration and openness.

4.4.10 Q&A in Panel Discussion Session

Table 9: Q & A in Panel Discussion Session

Q&As in Panel Discussion Session	
<p>Question: Will battery technology support V2G?</p>	<p>Jan Cupal (Verbund): If it will become technically feasible, then we all need to support it, and only then it will make sense financially, but now it does not support an economic possible case. The control can be done by just increasing or reducing the speed of charging. This does not qualify as an energy problem really, but rather a problem of lack of interconnected business processes. Smart charging does not make sense now, neither for the driver nor for the energy actors, as there is no business connection among them (no business case that profits all). DSO is a regulated business; and we will not act against our commercial interest. If more load is needed the energy actors will build more. So, it really comes down on the need to interconnect the business processes. First step for the high demand of power (ultra-fast charging systems with 150 and 400kw each and more) was the super-fast charging, and here it makes sense to have a cooperation with the actors involved. NeMo involved smart exchange of CPO and power provider, but with no commercial framework. A business case for everyone involved needs be clear, otherwise it will not make sense for them. Charge demand is sent to CPO, and the CPO answers with the cost. In the future, you will select your CP based on cost. The current cost situation of the CPO is based on cost of power that is given to the CPO based on a complex contract. For a regulated energy system, now there is no incentive for DSOs to be integrated in such ways.</p>
	<p>Ichiro Sakai (HONDA): Indeed, there are issues as regards battery deterioration by discharging energy in inappropriate temperature. But it can be possible in terms of cash flow.</p>

Marc Bechler (HONDA):	We cannot dismiss the possibility from DSOs perspective, as in some countries problems with the energy supply are supported by such bidirectional solutions, for example this would be needed in India.
Jan Cupal (Verbund):	In the next years, I don't really see that happening in Europe, because the impact on the system, from the energy content of the batteries is not much, compared to what the grid capacity. But in terms of power, the impact is huge, once several charging sessions are happening.
Noshin Omar (AVESTA):	We are at the beginning of electrification, where capacities are limited and still not significant at the moment. In the near years, it will not be required, but in future the business model will be there. India worked on the perspective to stabilize the grid, because the impact in cost was high and they did it based on existing fleets of e-buses. The need is not really obvious for the near future.
Ichiro Sakai (HONDA):	All influencing factors need to be of course considered - like country and environment – but providing such service to the customer, to be able to utilise the battery is of added value, and we cannot dismiss the prospect.
Angel Lopez (BCN):	If we need EVs to regulate and complete the power, then we need a plug in every place a car can park, that the street cannot support. Most of charges will take place at garages off the street and this needs planning. Same eternal problem for the cities of where to park, space being always an issue for us, we need to plan the garages and the places to plug. The idea of the user owning and using his battery, when users will not need to own a car in the schemes of future shared mobility, why would it make sense to own a battery? Sharing fleets and other initiatives can be a part of the grid in this case. It's a problem of grid and energy market regulation but it is affecting the electromobility solution.
Noshin Omar (AVESTA):	Now it is not allowed to sell electricity to a third party, even if technology is there, energy is also regulated market. Being able to sell from my battery to the neighbour will take time for European regulations to change and include these schemes.
Jan Cupal (Verbund):	If we want to foster these technologies, we need to create business cases, simple so if you want to share electricity you will be able to. One application with a potential business case for V2G that could come first, is energizing your private house, feeding back to your own house, charging the battery from the RES on the rooftop. This will be the first business case that will emerge.
Ichiro Sakai (Honda):	This is within Honda scope, and if this is combined properly in this case, depending on several parameters, it might be very effective

for avoiding infrastructure cost or other costs that come down to the customer.

Christian HANN (Hsubject): You cannot be sure of the future, but we know that we need some flexibility and to improve the way we collaborate. It is a good time now to think how we can achieve this solution also. And support it by protocols, standards, etc., starting now.

Judit Bataye (SIX-TER, Ouishare) From the case of our car sharing initiatives, we have experienced the collaborative cases, including green energy, Wi-Fi, other solutions, etc., so we really can collaborate and this is what you are showing now in NeMo. It is clear that we need to have an open approach.

Annex I – Official Invitation Letter

NeMo Final Conference & Exhibition

"From project to market: seamless Electromobility services in Europe"

19 September 2019 | Barcelona, Spain

INVITATION

Dear Madam/dear Sir,

On behalf of the European Horizon 2020 project [NeMo](#) "Hyper-Network for Electromobility", I am very pleased to invite you to the project's Final Conference and Exhibition, organised in Barcelona, Spain, on Thursday, 19 September 2019.

Concluding three years of research and development, the consortium will showcase how NeMo makes Electromobility in the road sector more attractive for businesses and users, during a one-day conference and exhibition. The NeMo Final Event and Exhibition aims to bring together industry and e-roaming platforms representatives, academics and researchers, road, charging point and grid operators, solution providers and other Electromobility stakeholders, to share its results leading to the node-based Hyper-Network for Electromobility, the functionalities that it offers and its contribution towards seamless, interoperable and widely available services for all Electromobility actors.

Through a number of technical presentations, panel discussions, interactive demonstrations and hands-on sessions, prominent speakers from academia and industry as well as renowned experts in the field will present the key elements of the NeMo Hyper-Network. These elements include the NeMo Common Information Models, easy creation, execution and delivery of services on the Hyper-Network, as well as the smart horizontal services that NeMo has made available. In parallel, the Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol, which links different Electromobility roaming platforms and enables cross-provider Electromobility roaming seamlessly, will be on display; and the specific architecture developed for the Extended Vehicle and Neutral Server deployed via the project's OEMs, which assists the driver to experience improved services and access real vehicle data, will be presented to the attendees.

Join the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition to be among the first to learn about the project impacts on the Electromobility ecosystem and the partners' plans to continue the operation and development of NeMo's services through the establishment of an open association. Participants' interaction will be encouraged, during a panel discussion focusing on future needs for seamless Electromobility, while networking opportunities will be offered in the framework of the parallel exhibition.

Participation in the NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition is free, but registration is mandatory to secure your place. **To find out more and to register, please visit <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>.**

For further questions, please contact info@nemo-emobility.eu

I look forward to welcoming you in Barcelona, on the 19th of September!

Yours faithfully,

Dr. Angelos Amditis

NeMo Project Coordinator

Research Director,

Institute of Communication and Computer Systems (ICCS), Greece

This project has received funding by the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation program under grant agreement no 713794.

Annex II – Press Invitations (EN, ES)

Screenshot of the English version

**From project to market:
Seamless electromobility
services in Europe**

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
 Barcelona, 19th September 2019

Press invitation
NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition

Thursday 19 September 2019, 09:00-16:30
 Ca l'Alier
 Carrer de Pere IV, 362
 08019 Barcelona

Organised by:

Ajuntament de Barcelona
Event host

ERTICO
NeMo Dissemination Manager

ETIXEY ICGS
NeMo Project Coordinator

mosaicfactor
Event co-host

On behalf of the NeMo Project Consortium

 This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 713794

The partners of the European Horizon 2020 project NeMo "*Hyper-Network for Electromobility*" are pleased to invite you to the project's Final Conference and Exhibition, taking place in Barcelona, Spain, on Thursday, 19 September 2019.

As the NeMo project reaches its conclusion, this conference will present the result of three years of work by the consortium partners through technical presentations and a technology showcase featuring live demonstrations of electromobility services.

The conference will be introduced by a representative of the City of Barcelona, host of the event, who will give an overview of electromobility in the city.

The event agenda will feature in-depth presentations of:

- **The NeMo Hyper-Network: What it is and how it works**
- **The Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol**
- **Access to the NeMo Hyper-Network and business features of the NeMo Marketplace**
- **Followed by a panel discussion: "The future of electromobility"**

In addition to the Conference programme, participants will be able to visit an **exhibition area** showcasing different aspects of NeMo. **Live demonstrations** will include:

- **NeMo, the Blockchain-based Hyper-Network**
- **The NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node**
- **Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure**
- **End-to-end smart charging based on ISO 15118 and OCPP**
- **NeMo Battery Services, Service creation in the Hyper-Network**

The demonstrations will be accompanied by a series of technical posters.

The language of the conference is English.

We are happy to answer your queries and arrange interviews for you. For all queries, please contact Hugo Roebroek, NeMo Dissemination Manager, at h.roebroek@mail.ertico.com or +32 473 516 112.

Event registration and updates: <https://www.eventbrite.com/e/from-project-to-market-seamless-electromobility-services-in-europe-registration-61996854260>

For more information, visit <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>

Screenshot of the Spanish version

NeMo
Hyper-Network
for electroMobility

**From project to market:
Seamless electromobility
services in Europe**

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
Barcelona, 19th September 2019

Invitación de prensa

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition

Jueves 19 de septiembre 2019, 09:00-16:30
Ca l'Alíer
Carrer de Pere IV, 362
08019 Barcelona

Organizado por:

**Ajuntament
de Barcelona**

Event host

*NeMo Dissemination
Manager*

*NeMo Project
Coordinator*

mosaicfactor

Event co-host

On behalf of the NeMo Project Consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 713794

A los socios del proyecto europeo Horizonte 2020 NeMo "Hyper-Network for Electromobility" les complace invitarlo a la Conferencia y Exposición Final del proyecto, que tendrá lugar en Barcelona, España, el jueves 19 de septiembre de 2019..

A medida que el proyecto NeMo se acerca a su conclusión, esta conferencia presentará el resultado de tres años de trabajo de los socios del consorcio a través de presentaciones técnicas y una exhibición tecnológica con demostraciones en vivo de servicios de electromovilidad.

La conferencia será presentada por un representante de la ciudad de Barcelona, anfitrión del evento, que dará una visión general de la electromovilidad en la ciudad.

La agenda del evento contará con presentaciones detalladas de:

- **La Hyper-Network de NeMo: Qué es y cómo funciona.**
- **The Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol**
- **Acceso a la Hyper-Network de NeMo y a las funciones comerciales del mercado de NeMo**
- **Seguido por una mesa redonda: "El futuro de la electromovilidad"**

Además del programa de la conferencia, los participantes podrán visitar el área de exhibición donde se mostrarán diferentes aspectos de NeMo. Las demostraciones en vivo incluirán:

- **NeMo, the BlockChain-based Hyper-Network**
 - *NeMo, la Hiper-Network basada en BlockChain*
- **The NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node**
 - *El mercado de NeMo y el nodo de ejecución*
- **Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure**
 - *Servidor neutral y estándar de Vehículo Extendido integrado con la infraestructura de NeMo*
- **End-to-end smart charging based on ISO 15118 and OCPP**
 - *Carga inteligente de extremo a extremo basada en ISO 15118 y OCPP*
- **NeMo Battery Services, Service creation in the Hyper-Network**
 - *Servicios de baterías NeMo, Creación de servicios en la Hiper-Red*

Las demostraciones estarán acompañadas por una serie de posters técnicos.

El idioma de la conferencia es el inglés

Nos complace responder a sus consultas y concertar entrevistas para usted. Para todas las consultas, comuníquese con Hugo Roebroek, Gerente de Difusión de NeMo, a través del email h.roebroek@mail.ertico.com o llamando al +32 473 516 112.

Registro en el evento y actualizaciones: <https://www.eventbrite.com/e/from-project-to-market-seamless-electromobility-services-in-europe-registration-61996854260>

Para obtener más información, visite <https://nemo-emobility.eu/conference>

Annex III – Conference Agenda

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition – Agenda

Hyper-Network for electroMobility

**From project to market:
Seamless electromobility
services in Europe**

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition

Thursday 19 September 2019, 09:00-18:30
Ca l'Alfer
Carrer de Pere IV, 362
08019 Barcelona

Organised by:

Event host

*NeMo Dissemination
Manager*

*NeMo Project
Coordinator*

Event co-host

On behalf of the NeMo Project Consortium

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement no 713794

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition – Agenda Thursday, 19 September 2019

Event language: English

Time	Item	Presenter
09:00-09:30	Registration / Coffee	
09:30-10:00	Conference opening session	
09:30	<i>Welcome from the host and overview of Electromobility in the City of Barcelona</i>	Senior representative from Ajuntament de Barcelona / City of Barcelona
09:40	<i>Overview of NeMo achievements</i>	Evangelia Portouli, ICCS – Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
10:00-11:30	Conference session: Creating a Hyper-Network for Electromobility	
10:00	<i>NeMo Hyper-Network: What it is and how it works</i>	Thomas Walz, IBM Deutschland
10:15	<i>Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol</i>	Thomas Fousse, Gireve
10:35	<i>NeMo Common Information Models</i>	Christina Anagnostopoulou, ICCS
10:45	<i>Easy service creation</i>	Nils Masuch, Technical University of Berlin
10:50	<i>Smart services for electromobility</i>	Stefano Persi, Mosaic Factor
11:00	<i>Evaluation activities and NeMo impact:</i>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> NeMo test sites, the European Electromobility Test Drive and the NeMo Hackathon 	Christophe Maure, Applus+ IDIADA
11:20	<i>From NeMo to a Business Alliance for Electromobility</i>	Andrew Winder, ERTICO – ITS Europe
11:30-11:50	Coffee break / Exhibition visit	
11:50-13:00	Conference session: Business and Technical showcase of the NeMo Hyper-Network	
11:50	<i>Using the Hyper-Network: Access and business features of the NeMo Marketplace</i>	Thomas Walz, IBM Deutschland
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Partner on-boarding, Marketplace functionality 	
12:05	<i>Technical presentation of the Hyper-Network</i>	
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Registration of an atomic or horizontal service. Service offering and contracting 	Thomas Fousse, Gireve
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Creation of a composite service: Charging point search based on mobility needs 	Nils Masuch, Technical University of Berlin
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Service execution, with focus on integration bus and Translators 	Thodoris Theodoropoulos, ICCS
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Demonstration of a use case: Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure 	Roberto Tola, CRF – Centro Ricerche Fiat
13:00-14:00	Lunch break / Exhibition visit	
14:00-15:30	Conference session: Panel discussion and conclusions	
14:00	<i>Panel discussion: "The future of electromobility"</i>	Àngel López, Ajuntament de Barcelona
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Viewpoints and open discussion including representatives of different stakeholder types (public authority, electromobility roaming provider, energy sector, automotive sector, service providers) 	Christian Hahn, Hubeject Jean-Marc Rives, Gireve Jan Cupal, VERBUND Ichiro Sakai, Honda Alexander Kröller, TomTom
	Moderated by Evangelia Portouli, ICCS	Noshin Omar, Avesta Battery & Energy Engineering
15:00	<i>Conclusions</i>	Evangelia Portouli, ICCS
15:30-16:30	Networking drinks reception / Exhibition area remains open	
	<p><i>The exhibition area will showcase different aspects of NeMo, including technical posters and the opportunity to talk to NeMo partners who will be giving the following demonstrations:</i></p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> <i>NeMo the Blockchain based Hyper-Network: the NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node</i>, by IBM <i>Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure</i>, by CRF <i>Demonstration of Double Consent functionality to get User consensus for Neutral Server integration in the Extended Vehicle system</i>, by Honda R&D Europe <i>Software for charge points enabling end-to-end communication for smart charging</i>, by BroadBit <i>NeMo Battery Services</i>, by fia <i>Service creation in the Hyper-Network</i>, by Technical University of Berlin <i>ChargeSharing: a community-based charging solution for EV drivers</i>, by eCharge <p>See below for further details.</p>	

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition – Panel discussion speakers

Dr. Evangelia Portouli

Senior Researcher, ICCS (Greece)

She holds a Mechanical Engineer degree with excellence from the National Technical University of Athens and a PhD on Cognitive ergonomics from the same Institute. She is a Senior Researcher and leader of the Administration, Quality and Dissemination of the I-SENSE Group of ICCS. In the period 1991-1994 she has worked in an industrial company, designing and developing prototype systems for vehicles. Since 1994 she has worked as research consultant on intelligent transportation systems. In the period 2005-2010 she has worked as researcher in the Hellenic Institute of Transport of the Centre for Research and Technology Hellas. Her scientific interests include the ergonomic design and development of driving automation and support systems

Àngel López Rodríguez

Director of Electromobility strategy, City of Barcelona (Spain)

PhD Àngel López Rodríguez currently serves as Director of Barcelona's Electric Vehicle Program and Executive Director of the LIVE Platform, a public-private partnership that aims at promoting sustainable urban mobility in Barcelona. Prior to this, Mr. López served as Director for Mobility and Infrastructure at Barcelona City Council.

In the past, he worked in major projects for the city councils of Madrid and Barcelona, the Catalanian regional government, the Spanish Directorate of Traffic (DGT) and the Spanish Ministry of Public Works, and had management responsibilities in private high-tech companies. His areas of expertise include traffic management, road safety and public transport systems. He holds a MSc and a PhD in civil engineering from Polytechnic University of Catalonia.

Christian Hahn

CEO, Hsubject GmbH (Germany)

His career began at ThyssenKrupp and Daimler AG, followed by six years at PricewaterhouseCoopers in Berlin, where he specialized in consulting for the energy supply business. He began working on his first electric vehicle projects in 2008. He joined Hsubject in 2012, where he started as Head of Business Development and Administration and in 2015 Christian was appointed CEO of Hsubject GmbH. Following a change in the management team in January 2019, his primary focus is now on strategy, investor relations, and the global Hsubject company setup.

Jean-Marc Rives

Chief Technical Officer, Gireve (France)

Jean-Marc gained a long experience on IT and innovation projects at Renault company. At GIREVE, since 2013, he leads the technical part and the new services. He is also involved in several e-mobility-related research projects.

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition – Panel discussion speakers

Jan Cupal

Senior Innovation Manager, VERBUND (Austria)

Jan Cupal has been almost 12 years in VERBUND in Vienna, where he is Senior Innovation Manager in Business Development E-Mobility & Smart Grids, and was previously Senior Expert Corporate Development in VERBUND.

Verbund

Ichiro Sakai

General Manager, Honda Motor Europe Ltd (Belgium)

A graduate of Osaka Prefectural University with a master's degree in system engineering, Sakai joined Honda R&D Co., Ltd. in Japan in 1985. Since then, he has, among others worked in emission engineering and regulatory affairs in the USA and the EU. In 2018, he was appointed as the Japanese liaison engineer in Brussels where he works on regulatory issues in collaboration with stakeholders in an industry as well as in the EU institutions.

HONDA

Alexander Kröller

Research Manager, TomTom (Germany)

Alexander Kröller is leading TomTom's navigation research & innovation team, and responsible for collaborative research projects. He is also heading TomTom Lab, TomTom's company-wide innovation program. Before that, he pursued an academic career in algorithms.

TOMTOM

Noshin Omar

CEO and Founder, ABEE – Avesta Battery & Energy Engineering (Belgium)

Managing director of ABEE with 14 years' experience in R&D projects. He obtained his PhD degree in electromechanical Engineering Sciences from the Vrije Universiteit Brussel in the field of Li-ion batteries for automotive applications. Sinds 2012 until March 2019, he was the Director of the Battery Innovation Center at the Vrije Universiteit Brussel, where he was leading a team of 30 researchers in the field of energy storage. Over the last 14 years he has been active in various national and European projects in the field of characterisation, electrical, thermal, electrochemical and lifetime modelling of various rechargeable energy storage systems. He is very active in the field of European funded projects. He has more than 200 publications.

ABEE

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition – Demonstrations

NeMo: the Blockchain based Hyper-Network.

The NeMo Marketplace and Execution Node: What it is and how it works.

IBM, Technical University of Berlin, ICCS

Contact: Thomas.Walz@de.ibm.com

A live demonstration of what the NeMo network and its Nodes comprises.

What NeMo partner and user roles are available with respective access control.

What features are available to business .

In particular this will demonstrate how a service consumer or service provider, can access a NeMo Node, how he finds and contracts a service and how to register a service and create a respective service offering via the NeMo Marketplace.

Demonstration of Double Consent functionality to get User consensus for Data Provision

Honda R&D Europe

Contact: Marc_Bechler@de.hrdev.com

An important aspect in the Extended Vehicle standard, the Neutral Server concept and the NeMo Hyper-Network is the availability of vehicle data for the 3rd party service provider. Therefore, the driver must have the choice to decide with whom he or she wants to share this data. In this demonstration, we show how a driver can selectively share her or his vehicle data using the "Double Consent" concept in a very comfortable and transparent way; and we also show how 3rd party providers can make use of this concept for service provision.

Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure

CRF, IBM, TomTom, Renault

Contact: roberto.tola@crf.it

A specific architecture for an Extended Vehicle and Neutral Server developed by NeMo, following the relevant work by ACEA (the European Automobile Manufacturers Association) and ISO. It was deployed by CRF (Centro Ricerche Fiat), Renault and Honda. A key aspect is that the driver consents twice to sharing data from the electric vehicle with an external service provider through the Neutral Server and the NeMo Hyper-Network. In this way, the driver experiences improved services, as the service provider has access to real vehicle data.

Service Creation

Technical University of Berlin (DAI-Labor), fka, Politecnico di Bari

Contact: Nils.Masuch@dai-labor.de

Demonstration of the ceation of a composite service: Charging point search based on mobility needs.

NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition – Demonstrations

NeMo Battery Services

fka GmbH

Contact: joerg.kuefen@fka.de

Software for charge points enabling end-to-end communication for smart charging

BroadBit

Contact: adam.knapp@broadbit.net

Our solution demonstrates end-to-end communication through the EV – Recharging station – Central System entities providing smart charging features, like plug-and-charge, scheduled recharging, authentication, power balancing, rate negotiation etc. The key contribution is the software component developed for charge points that seamlessly integrates the ISO 15118 protocol and the Open Charge Point Protocol (OCPP). It can be considered as the “last mile” of NeMo Hyper-network up to the vehicles. The demo reflects predefined use cases of the project related to smart charging.

ChargeSharing solution integrated into the NeMo Hyper-Network (NeMo Hackathon winner)

e3charge

Contact: info@e3charge.net

ChargeSharing from e3charge is a community-based network of private electric charging station providers. It allows owners of private charge points to rent out their use to others, without the user needing to create a new subscription or download a new app, but instead using standard well-known payment providers. The technical solution enables data on such charge points to be published in various charging station directories (online mapping) as well as in-vehicle navigation systems.

This application was judged the winner of the NeMo hackathon and e3charge was invited to the Final Conference to demonstrate the service, and how it has been integrated into the Hyper-Network.

Creating a Hyper Network for Electromobility (10:00 – 11:30)

Thomas Walz, IBM Deutschland - (10.00) <i>NeMo Hyper-Network, what it is and how it works</i>	NeMo Hyper-Network, what it is and how it works
Thomas Fousse, Gireve - (10.15) <i>Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol</i>	Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol
Christina Anagnostopoulou, ICCS - (10.35) <i>NeMo Common Information Models</i>	NeMo Common Information Models
Nils Masuch, TUB - (10.45) <i>Service Creation</i>	Service Creation
Stefano Persi, Mosaic - (10.50) <i>Smart Horizontal Services</i>	Smart Horizontal Services
Christophe Moure (IDIADA) - (11.00) <i>Evaluation activities and NeMo impact</i>	Evaluation Activities and NeMo Impact
Edouard Caumont (Renault) & Andrew Winder (ERTICO) - (11.20) <i>After NeMo Building BAEM</i>	After NeMo Building BAEM

Business & Technical Demonstrations of the NeMo Hyper-Network (11:50 – 13:00)

<p>Thomas Volk (BMW) - (11:50) Using the Hyper-Network: Access and business features of the NeMo Marketplace Partner onboarding</p>	<p>Using the Hyper-Network: Access and business features of the NeMo Marketplace</p>
<p>Thomas Fassek (GEMVE) - (12:00) Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network Registration of an atomic or horizontal service, Service offering and contracting</p>	<p>Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network</p>
<p>Sebastian Tala (OPF) Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network Creation of a composite service; Changing point search based on mobility needs</p>	<p>Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network</p>
<p>Theodor Thodoropoulos (CCI) Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network Service execution, with focus on Integration Bus and Translators</p>	<p>Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network</p>
<p>Sebastian Tala (OPF) Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network Demonstration of a use case: Neutral server and Embedded Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo Infrastructure</p>	<p>Technical Demonstration of the Hyper-Network</p>

Panel Discussion (14.00 – 15:30)

Ángel López, Barcelona Regional <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Christian Hahn, HUBject <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Jean-Marc Rives, Gireve <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Jan Cupal, VERBUND <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Ichiro Sakai, Honda <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Alexander Kröllner, TomTom <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Nashin Omar, Avesta <i>Panel Discussion</i>		Q&A
Evangelia Portouli <i>Conclusions</i>		Q&A

Annex V – PowerPoint Presentations (original version)

[9:30 – 10:00] - Conference opening session

[09: 40] - Overview of NeMo achievements, Dr. Evangelia Portouli (ICCS)

NeMo PROJECT OVERVIEW AND ITS MAIN ACHIEVEMENTS

Dr. Evangelia Portouli
Institute of Communication and Computer Systems
NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

NeMo at a glance

Call Identifier: H2020-GV-2015

Topic: GV-8-2015 Electric vehicles' enhanced performance and integration into the transport system and the grid

EC funding: € 7.8 million

This project has received funding from the EU's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under GA no 769926

Duration: October 2016 – September 2019

19 partners

5 test sites & 1 cross-country demonstration

Coordinator: by ICCS [Institute of Communication and Computer Systems], Greece (Dr. Angelos Amditis, a.amditis@iccs.gr)

Website: <http://nemo-emobility.eu>

Join us at:

LinkedIn NeMo_Electro @NeMo_Electro

What were the challenges for NeMo?

NeMo's approach

Develop a **Hyper-Network of tools, models and services**, which will enable the provision of **seamless and interoperable electromobility services** creating an open, distributed and widely accepted ecosystem for e-mobility

✓ improved accessibility to charging infrastructure and ICT services through a **pan-European Inter-Roaming framework**

✓ facilitate increased availability, better planning and more secure electric grid operation

✓ create business opportunities (increased B2B connectivity)

NeMo's strategic objectives

- **Common Information Models**
- **Open APIs** to enable an **open B2B cloud Marketplace** for electromobility
- **Core system** for provision of electromobility services
- **Smart horizontal services**
- Services **self-certification** mechanism
- **Business Alliance** for ElectroMobility (BAEM)

Nemo Common Information Models

- One of the pillars of NeMo Hyper-Network is the possibility to exchange data using a common NeMo meta-language

NeMo Inter-Roaming protocol

The NeMo Inter-Roaming protocol is a functional protocol that enables:

- the **direct communication** between eRoaming platforms
- publishing of eRoaming platforms' services to the NeMo Hyper-Network, providing **eRoaming features**, like any other NeMo service

NeMo Hyper-Network

= Nemo Nodes operated by Business partners
All participants have access to the same data

Example services in NeMo

- Horizontal Hyper-Network services:**
- 1. Electromobility actors' monitoring and profiling
 - 2. Finder and optimiser
 - 3. Brokerage
 - 4. Service pricing (static and dynamic)
- EV driver / owner services:**
- 5. Smart navigation and journey planning
 - 6. Wireless authentication solution
- Grid related services:**
- 7. Navigation to Charging Point based on user and grid requirements
 - 8. Load management
 - 9. Load forecasting due to EV charging
- EV and battery related services:**
- 10. Adaptive SoC limit calculation
 - 11. Capacity calculation
 - 12. Vehicle preconditioning

The CRF/IBM Trustee / Neutral server: Dynamic access to vehicle data

- Secure and fair data access for 3rd parties including possibility of 3rd party anonymisation
- Data protection & data privacy through purpose-specific customer consent based on double consent mechanism

Services self-certification processes

- Self and continuous evaluation of the service (by a service certifier) in terms of:
 - Response time
 - Accuracy
 - Availability
- Evaluation obtained by users on:
 - Efficiency
 - Availability
 - Reliability
 - Easiness to use

NeMo Test sites

Five test sites across Europe to evaluate the NeMo results

Cross-country demonstration

- Study usability, acceptance, experience of real users with the NeMo developments
 - ✓ Itinerary Planning
 - ✓ Cross-provider border booking authorization and payment

Opening the Hyper-Network

The Business Alliance for Electro-Mobility (BAEM) will take over the Hyper-Network after the project end

NeMo impact

- ❖ Enable information exchange among all involved actors
- ❖ Easy creation and delivery to a wide audience of innovative, interoperable electromobility services via the Open Cloud Marketplace
- ❖ Enhanced driver satisfaction: "Charge anywhere & anytime" across Europe via a single identification, authorisation & payment method

- ✓ Improved **attractiveness of electric vehicles**
- ✓ **Facilitation of EVs mass adoption**

Thank you! Any Questions?

Dr. Evangelia Portouli
v.portouli@iccs.gr

[10:00 – 11:30] - Conference session: Creating a Hyper – Network for Electromobility

[10:00] - NeMo Hyper-Network: What it is and how it works, Thomas Walz (IBM Germany)

NEMO HYPER - NETWORK, WHAT IT IS AND HOW IT WORKS

Thomas Walz

Technical Relations Executive
IBM Germany
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

AGENDA NeMo Hyper-Network, What it is and How it works

- **NeMo IT challenges**
- **NeMo Main architecture principles**
 - NeMo and Open Source
 - NeMo the Hyper-Network
 - Architecture of a single NeMo Node,
 - NeMo Partner Types and Roles + User roles
- **NeMo Node deployment**
 - NeMo Hyper-Network as of September 2019
- **Standards around NeMo Services**
- **End to end use case overview**
 - Use case and benefits using NeMo project
- **Summary and conclusion**

NeMo IT Challenges:

- ❑ How to develop **interoperable** and seamless electro-mobility services **without a central hosted system**
- ❑ Integration of services of **different stakeholders** still a challenge due to **missing interoperability** and **discovery mechanisms**
- ❑ No **community based** IT environment existent that enables the search, development and deployment of **value-added services** for the E-Mobility domain
- ❑ Lack of **common information model** for all stakeholders
- ❑ Stakeholders and business partners **not visible / transparent across Europe**
- ❑ Still difficult to **establish collaboration and contracts** between stakeholders and business partners

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NeMo main architecture principles

- "Full" Business partners operate a NeMo Node providing the core functionality to participate in the NeMo Marketplace
- "Associated" Partners can access all NeMo features via "full" Partner Node
- Service provider business partners - host implementations of the e-mobility services they offer via NeMo separate from a NeMo Node
- Interaction between NeMo nodes and services
 - Replicate marketplace data across NeMo Nodes
 - Orchestrate service-to-service calls via NeMo's Integration Bus
- Use open Open Source where possible

NeMo Node open source components

- **Hyperledger Fabric**
 - an enterprise-grade permissioned distributed ledger framework for developing solutions and applications;
- **Hyperledger Composer**
 - an extensive, open development toolset and framework for developing blockchain applications
- **Loopback**
 - a highly extensible, open-source Node.js framework based on Express for creating REST APIs
- **Keycloak**
 - an open source Identity and Access Management solution aimed at modern applications and services. It makes it easy to secure applications and services with little to no code.
- **Spring Boot**
 - a framework for creating stand-alone, production-grade Spring based Applications that you can "just run".
- **Angular**
 - a platform and framework for building client applications in HTML and TypeScript

Architecture of a single NeMo Node

A scenario with multiple organizations interacting via the NeMo Hyper-Network

AGENDA

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NeMo Hyper-Network as of September 2019

"Full" and "Associated" Partners

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Use case 42 - Itinerary planner

An **objective** was to provide a recommendation to the European Commission on **how they can regulate access** to in-vehicle data using the **ExVe ISO standard** and a **Neutral Server**. This was the first real use case of using such technology within the ACEA (European Automobile Manufacturer Association) working groups. In fact, the itinerary planner is able to connect with a remote neutral server, collect data from the vehicle in real time and use them in the routing algorithm.

This is an example of a NeMo CIM compliant response received from the IBM neutral server:

```
{
  "battery_pct": 85,
  "longitude": "7.5435257",
  "vehicle_estimated_range": 0,
  "latitude": "45.08153",
  "speed_kph": 0,
  "vehicle_id": "VIN11114",
  "timestamp": "2019-04-05T13:32:54.683+0200",
  "pos_lat_lon": "45.08153,7.5435257",
  "partialODO": 19351
}
```


IBM offering 2 services to make Renault vehicle data available returning CIM compliant objects

Representation of the IBM Neutral Server V1&V2 in NeMo for CRF, Renault, Honda & TomTom application with 3 TomTom Services registered by TomTom as affiliated partner of Gireve

TomTom application

AGENDA

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Summary of NeMo accomplishments

- ✓ a **distributed marketplace** for trading and executing electro-mobility IT services based on Blockchain/Hyperledger technology
- ✓ a **common information model** to unify the business objects for all electro-mobility services and thus foster service inter-operability
- ✓ a **development environment** for creating e-mobility services **employing semantic search techniques** for finding suitable services
- ✓ a **reference network of 8 NeMo nodes** where business partners can develop, trade and execute their e-mobility services
- ✓ a **collection of 25+ e-mobility services** published to the NeMo Marketplace
- ✓ a **technical foundation** for a Business Alliance for Electro-Mobility

Thank you! Any
Questions?

Thomas Walz
 Technical Relations Executive
IBM, Germany
Thomas.Walz@de.ibm.com

VCARD

[10:15] - Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol, Thomas Fousse (GIREVE)

OPEN EUROPEAN INTER-ROAMING PROTOCOL

Thomas FOUSSE
GIREVE
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Recharge-service Roaming : Access interoperability

A customer of eMobility Services Provider "A" wants access to a charging-station of Charge point Operator "B"

Recharge-service Roaming : Access interoperability

Connecting eMSPs and CPOs for which features? To exchange which data? which services ?

Roaming : Two main topologies ...

Internal management of complexity
IT – Contracts negotiation and follow-up – Invoicing/Payment ...

External management of complexity
IT – Contracts negotiation and follow-up – Invoicing/Payment ...

Roaming : Two main topologies that can be merged

**Roaming : Two main topologies ...
... that can be merged and integrated ...**

**Roaming : Two main topologies ...
... that can be merged and integrated thanks to NeMo**

First Nemo's contribution

- Setting a "Inter Roaming Platform Framework"
- Connecting 2 of them (Gireve and Hubject)

Increase the number of accessible Charging Points

**Roaming : A big challenge about standardisation ...
... simplified by Nemo**

eMobility IT protocol

- OCPI, eMIP, OICP, OCHP...

eMobility business objects

- Contracts, Tariffs, CDRs

Nemo hyper Network

- Standardised access, based on
- **A Common Information Model**
- **Open IT access & interfaces**
- **New services creation & deployment features**

1 Developing the base roaming protocol

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2 Developments and tests of Inter Roaming NeMo services

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Business model

Contractual terms specified in NeMo Work Package 7

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Open European Inter-Roaming Protocol

Thomas FOUSSE
GIREVE
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

[10:35] - NeMo Common Information Models, Christina Anagnostopoulou (ICCS)

NEMO COMMON INFORMATION MODELS

Christina Anagnostopoulou
Institute of Communication and Computer
Systems
NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Rationale of the work

- Lack of Interoperability in electromobility services
- Lack of a common data and information model for objects and services
 - typically, proprietary software and data formats to communicate/exchange necessary information
 - proprietary data management and interfacing between actors
- Lack of standardisation regarding information exchange and services provision
- Electromobility actors are diverse

Common Information Models

- Models of physical objects and data structures which are relevant for the use cases selected in the project
- Based on previous relevant work, integrate existing standards on information modelling related to electromobility
- Create a consistent format for data to be available to others

Location in the Hyper-Network

- New services will generate and exchange data according to the CIM
- Data translators will enable the translation of data to the NeMo CIM

Methodology

- Based on electromobility information modelling (7 NeMo Business Scenarios)
- Identification of Business Objects (physical entities and data structures) that need modelling
- Definition of attributes per Business Object (name, definition, necessity, instances, format)
- Used the template of the eMi³ Electric Vehicle ICT Interface Specifications Part 2 (Charging infrastructure/charge detail record objects)

Business Objects categorisation

- Electric Vehicle
- Charging Infrastructure
- Final User
- Charge Session
- Smart Charging Functionalities
- Marketplace for service creation and delivery
- Grid loads
- Vehicle preparation for drive-off
- Support Business Objects

Business Objects categorisation

- Electric Vehicle

- Information may come from different sources, for example the Neutral Server or a NeMo service
- Battery
 - BatteryID, VIN, BatteryType, BatteryCapacity, SoC, SoH, BatteryFault, ChargeCompletionEstimatedTime, ChargingStatus
- Vehicle
 - VIN, Manufacturer, VehicleModel, ChargingMode, MaxPower, VehiclePower, VehicleRange, VehicleSpeed, VehicleODO, VehicleConsumption, VehicleRemainingDistance, CurrentLocation, DestinationLocation, ExternalTemperature, VehicleHeatingStatus, VehicleACStatus, PreconditioningFunctionalities

Business Objects categorisation

• Smart Charge

- **UserMobilityNeed**
 - data structure that is sent from an EMP or from a customer's device, in order to schedule a charging session for an EV before the next trip
- **UserChargeNeed**
 - calculated energy needs for the customer's vehicle to perform the trip planned in the customer's request
- **ChargeProposition**
 - data structure with a list of EVSEs and offered charging profiles that can cover the customer's request
- **ChargePropositionDetail**
 - one offered charging profile and cost
- **PropositionReservationRequest**
- **VariableOffers**
 - information relevant to the electricity grid, i.e. available power, maximum energy and price for charging per day and time in a specific area

Business Objects categorisation

• Charge session

- **Authorisation**
- **ChargeDetailRecord**
 - models the information about a finished charge session (update of the eMI³ model)
- **ChargingPeriodRecord**
 - One charging session consists of one or more charging periods

Business Objects categorisation

• Marketplace

- **ServiceContract**
 - signed between two entities
- **ContractSection**
- **Terms**
- **BusinessPartner**
- **BusinessPartnerInformation**
- **AdditionalID**
- **Service**
 - semantic service description exists within an OWL-S description that is referenced from the Object
- **Category**
 - hierarchy allowing to navigate through the service catalogue
- **ServiceContractOffering**

Business Objects categorisation

- EV User

- User
- UserProfile
 - Preferences, history, recurrent places and trips
- UserChargingPreferences
- UserDrivingPreferences
- UserAgenda

Business Objects categorisation

- eMobility Reporting

- GetLoadReport
 - data structure sent by an authority or energy retailer, to get the list of CDRs and the energy delivered per EVSE for a specific time period
- CPOLoadReport
- LoadDetails
- AreaLoadReport
- PoDDemand
 - energy demand per DSO fiscal smart meter with time

Business Objects categorisation

- Vehicle preparation

- FleetMobilityNeed
- VehiclePredictedEnergyNeed
- PreconditioningProfile
 - notifications for the preparation of vehicle functionalities
- VehicleFunctionNotification

Business Objects categorisation

- EV Charging infrastructure

- ChargingConnector
- EVSE (or Charging Point) can charge one EV at a time
- ChargingStation, is a physical object with a User Interface
- ChargingPool, one or more Charging Stations operated by one CPO

Support Objects

- AddressInfo
- AdminState
- Appointment
- Contact
- CostOffer
- ChargingProfile
- ChargingProfilePeriod
- CPO
- EnergyTime
- GeoCoordinate
- ItinerarySection
- LocationInfo
- OpenHours
- OperationalState
- ParkingInfo
- PowerTime
- RecurrentUserPlace
- RecurrentUserTrip
- TimeFrequency
- TimePeriod
- Trip
- UserComments

Examples

UserMobilityNeed

ATTRIBUTE	DEFINITION	INST.	M/O	Format
eMAID	eMobility Account Identifier, as in ISO/IEC 15118.	1	M	string
RequestID	This is a unique identifier of the request	1	M	string
ItinerarySections	The list of itinerary sections that comprise the next trip	n	M	List of complex "ItinerarySection"
Vehicle	This is a reference to the description of the vehicle.	1	O	complex "Vehicle"
ItineraryEnergyNeed	This is a list of the energy need (in kWh) of the vehicle at the start of each itinerary section in order to complete the next itinerary section	n	M	List of double
TripEnergyNeed	This is the total energy need (in kWh) of the vehicle in order to complete the next trip	1	M	double

CIM via NeMo components

Phase I: Service creation

Generation of the translation transformation logic to be used during service invocation based on: bidirectional PSM-to-CIM mapping, services semantic annotation (service creation tools), service registration

Phase II: Service invocation

Execution of the transformation workflow generated during Phase I on service request/response messages, dynamic services search and execution

Conclusions

- Common Information Models for electromobility business objects
 - Enable information exchange among all involved actors
 - Data translators will enable the translation of data to the NeMo CIM
 - New services will generate and exchange data according to the CIM
 - Integration of smart services
- Liaison with standardization groups - eMi³
- CIM second version is released

Thank you! Any Questions?

Christina Anagnostopoulou
ICCS
christina.anagnostopoulou@iccs.gr

[10:45] - Easy service creation, Nils Masuch (Technical University Berlin)

EASY SERVICE CREATION

Nils Masuch
Technical University Berlin
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

What is Service Creation in NeMo?

- Supporting the integration of existing services into the NeMo Network

What is Service Creation in NeMo?

- Supporting the integration of existing services into the NeMo Network

What is Service Creation in NeMo?

- Supporting the integration of existing services into the NeMo Network

What is Service Creation in NeMo?

- Supporting the creation of composite services that rely on several services provided via NeMo Network

What is Service Creation in NeMo?

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- Supporting the creation of composite services that rely on several services provided via NeMo Network

How does NeMo support creating Composite Services?

- Provision of a toolchain from first idea to finalized service

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How can I use these tools?

- Tools integrated in eclipse
- Available as a docker image for easy deployment
- Tools available on dockerhub
- More Details @ Technical Session (11:50 am)

Thank you!
Any Questions?

Nils Masuch
Technical University Berlin

[10:50] - Smart Electromobility Services, Stefano Persi (Mosaic Factor)

SMART SERVICES FOR ELECTROMOBILITY

Stefano Persi
Mosaic Factor
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Agenda

- B2B Marketplace for electromobility services
- Benefits of the marketplace
- NeMo Services use cases
- Service Brokerage

B2B Marketplace for electromobility services

Services provide added-on functionality usable in the whole environment

Benefits of the marketplace

Provide seamless interoperability of B2B and B2C electromobility services

SERVICE PROVIDERS

- Provide a set of new and existing services
- Easy to publish
- Combine different services to give added value to the users
- Get a better knowledge of users

EMOBILITY USERS

- Access to global services
- Single platform/interface
- Easy to access
- Combine different services
- eRoaming interoperability

NeMo Services use cases

DAILY COMMUTE

- Service Brokerage**
 - All the users' requests to existing services
- Smart navigation**
 - Availability and location of CPs
 - Road traffic and
 - Battery SOC
- CPO monitoring and profiling**
 - CP availability
 - Irregular activity
 - Generate valuable personal and non-personal information
- EV driver monitor and profiling**
 - Mobility patterns
 - User interests
 - Generate valuable personal and non-personal information
- Smart Journey Planner**
 - Route planning

OCCASIONAL TRIPS

- Rating/pricing services**
- CP Booking**
- Smart navigation**
 - Route calculation
 - CP availability
 - Required EV charge time
 - Battery SOC
- Wireless authentication service**
 - Access control
 - Identification, authentication and authorization
- CPO monitoring and profiling**
 - CP availability
 - Irregular activity
 - Generate valuable personal and non-personal information

CP Prediction

CP usage historical & real-time information

SHORT & LONG-TERM PREDICTION

Service Brokerage (I)

Service Brokerage (III)

Thank you! Any
Questions?

Stefano Persi
CEO of Mosaic Factor
stefano.persi@mosaicfactor.com
www.mosaicfactor.com

[11:00] - Evaluation activities and NeMo impact, Christophe Moure (Applus IDIADA)

EVALUATION ACTIVITIES AND NEMO IMPACT

Christophe Moure
Applus IDIADA
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Agenda

- Validation of the NeMo HyperNetwork
- Evaluation activities in test sites
- European Electromobility Test Drive

Validation of the NeMo HyperNetwork NeMo Hackaton

- Purpose
 - Evaluation of the effectiveness of the Hyper-Network open tools for services creation
 - Validation of the NeMo APIs
 - Verification the added value of horizontal services
 - Validation of the easiness of data integration
 - Engagement of external organizations, especially external service developers
- Process
 - Open call in March 2019 and winner announcement in June 2019

Validation of the NeMo HyperNetwork NeMo Hackaton

- Selection of 2 services
 - Pick&Pak: Car share & luggage share service proposed by Pooja Rangarajan
 - ChargeSharing solution proposed by e3Charge
- Final results according to Hackaton criteria
 - e3charge: 9/12
 - Pick and pack: 6.25/12

Evaluation activities in test sites

- 5 test sites with different scenarios

Evaluation activities in test sites Italian test site

- Purposes of the itinerary planning
 - Navigation system with notifications to the driver
 - Courtesy assistant app to offer advantages to highway users
- Test description
 - 14 naïve users as drivers
 - Journey from CRF facilities to Bardonecchia
 - Evaluation of the complete service
- Main outputs
 - Service highly appreciated by the users
 - Easiness to visualize and book charging points

Evaluation activities in test sites Austrian test site

- Purposes of the microgrid management
 - Optimizing the power costs for a high power charge point with stationary battery
- Test description
 - Simulation of 3 charge points in different locations (Vienna, Innsbruck, and Feldkirchen)
 - Measurement data from another funded project called SYNERG-E
 - Energy cost study considering different configurations
- Main outputs
 - Economic optimization up to 8% for a single charge point

Evaluation activities in test sites

German test site

- Purposes of the battery services
 - Offer new services related to the battery for end users
 - Improve exiting features of the BMS
- Test description
 - Simulation of end users, BMS and vehicle based on real data
 - Development of a specific device for testing the overall process

- Main outputs
 - Utility of the service highly appreciated
 - Complex topic to manage as standalone in vehicles today

Evaluation activities in test sites

French test site

- Purposes of the itinerary planning
 - Fetching vehicle data in a single way
 - Providing the best route to the driver based on charge points and EV real time data

- Test description
 - ACEA demonstration as concept of extended vehicle in CRF facilities
 - Participation of NeMo partners and an external OEM

- Main outputs
 - Utility of the service highly appreciated
 - Possibilities to link with many other services like charge point booking

Evaluation activities in test sites

Spanish test site

- Purposes of the actor profiling/brokerage services
 - Assisting end users choosing the right charging station in terms of availability and price
 - Avoiding system congestions due to high demand of specific resources

- Test description
 - Simulation of many users based on real data
 - Study of occupancy and collisions with/without broker

- Main outputs
 - Information highly appreciated by the end users
 - Possibilities to link with other services like EMPs apps or charge point booking

European Electromobility Test Drive

- Purposes of the test drive
 - Evaluate the inter-roaming protocol benefits in field
 - Route crossing several with different CPOs and EMPs
 - Dissemination event all along the test drive

First test drive route

- Test description
 - 2 test drives organized to evaluate the European charging context with/without inter-roaming
 - October 2017: 950km from Turin to Barcelona with 2 vehicles
 - May-June 2019: 5000km with 1 vehicle

European Electromobility Test Drive

- Second test drive in numbers
 - 1 electric vehicle
 - 14 drivers from 6 countries
 - 5000 km in total
 - 9 countries
 - 1 month duration
 - Stops in 4 major events and 5 NeMo pilot sites

Second test drive route

- Main outputs
 - Significant improvement of driver satisfaction thanks to the inter-roaming protocol

Thank you! Any Questions?

Christophe Moure
Project Manager
EV & HEV / Powertrain
christophe.moure@idiada.com

Applus⁺
IDIADA

YOUR DEVELOPMENT PARTNER

[11:20] - From NeMo to a Business Alliance for Electromobility, Andrew Winder (ERTICO – ITS Europe)

FROM NEMO TO A BUSINESS ALLIANCE FOR ELECTROMOBILITY

Andrew Winder
ERTICO – ITS Europe
NeMo Final Conference and Exhibition
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The Business Alliance for ElectroMobility (BAEM)

Why?

- To build a solid future for the Hyper-Network and associated services after the project end via a self-sustaining business model.

Vision:

- To promote interoperability of electromobility services via participation in standardisation processes.
- To act as a central operational hub in Europe for all electromobility actors, offering intelligence and added value via a unique marketplace.

The Business Alliance for ElectroMobility (BAEM)

What and who?

- A not-for-profit membership association (legal entity) comprising NeMo partners and other actors
- Open to all relevant stakeholders (membership MoU and fee)
- The BAEM will ensure full exploitation of the NeMo Hyper-Network and services.

BAEM value proposition

PROVIDE COMPETITIVENESS

EASE THE CREATION OF INNOVATIVE EMOBILITY SERVICES

BAEM customer/partner segments

BAEM value proposition for selected segments

Consumer	Offer
OEM	Add value to Customer data by giving access to Third Parties Provide Advanced EV services embedded in the car
Charge Point Operators	Provide dynamic pricing to your customers based on traffic influence or local grid capacity Connection to EMSPs by OCPP or through eRoaming platform State of the art EV services (booking, smart charging) and access to high level quality services
eMSP	Access to accurate ePCI Data in one click Be able to develop Advanced EV services for customers (itinerary planning, smart charging)
Energy players	Exploit EV charging to provide new services for grid stability and balancing purposes Be able to provide your customers EV with tailored offers and dynamic pricing Introduce more flexibility in the grid
Navigation provider	Getting data from EVs and charging point to provide Advanced itinerary planning for customers Be able to get EV data from multiple OEM with the same structure
Public authorities	Provide incentives for your people (free tolls, parking) Access to usage data to improve charging stations location

BAEM key activities

BAEM revenue streams and subscription models

Invitation to the BAEM

- Go to <https://nemo-emobility.eu/nemo-forum/> and click on the tab "Join NeMo"
- Register your interest in joining the Hyper-Network as a developer, provider or user of services
- Join us in setting up the BAEM as a founder member, to ensure sustainable management of the Hyper-Network after September 2019

Thank you!

Andrew Winder
a.winder@mail.ertico.com

[11:50 – 13:00] - Conference session: Business and technical demonstration of the NeMo Hyper-Network

[11:50] - Using the Hyper Network: Access and business features of the NeMo marketplace, Thomas Walz (IBM Germany) – Business Demonstration

BUSINESS AND TECHNICAL DEMONSTRATIONS OF THE NEMO HYPER-NETWORK

Thomas Walz

Technical Relations Executive
IBM Germany
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

AGENDA

Using the Hyper-Network: Access and business features of the NeMo Marketplace

- Recap NeMo Hyper-Network Architecture and current deployment
- NeMo partner type and partner & user roles
- How to join the NeMo as “full” or “associated” partner
 - Process and UI
- The NeMo Marketplace - Access & features
 - Marketplace login and navigation overview
 - Important Information (role, mode, Partner Type Navigation Tabs...)
 - How to search for a service
 - Service info
 - Overview on
 - Service registration, Service offering, Service contracting
- Monitoring the nodes with IBM Sysdig

Architecture of a single NeMo Node

NeMo HyperNetwork as of September 2019 „full“ and „associated“ Partners

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Roles of partners in the NeMo business network

NeMo partner Types

- Full NeMo Partner - Marketplace participant – operates a NeMo Node
- Affiliated NeMo partner - Marketplace participant – accesses NeMo features via full partner's NeMo Node

NeMo partner Roles

- NeMo Governance - can create/update/delete a BP
- Service Provider - can register services and publish commercial offerings for their services
- Service Consumer - can sign Service Contracts based on available Offerings
- Offerings Regulator - can see ServiceContracts signed by parties
- Service Prosumer - can act like Service Provider + Service Consumer

Roles of users in the NeMo business network

Activities of users of the NeMo Marketplace for e-mobility IT Services

Role	Activity
Business Administrator	manages NeMo account of a BP
Service Developer	implements and registers NeMo services
Offering Manager	maintains the service offerings of a BP
Contract Manager	manages the service contracts of a BP
Technical Administrator	The super user of a BP; - node installation and operation - all what the others can do

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How to join NeMo as "full" or "associated" partner

Application Process:

- Contact NeMo Coordinator (see WebSite : <https://nemo-emobility.eu/nemo-forum/>)
- Bilateral discussion with NeMo Coordinator and your partner in case of "affiliated" partner approach
- Sign Memorandum of understanding
- Get registered
- Install NeMo Node
 - Or get access via full partner node

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The NeMo Marketplace - Access & features

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How to join NeMo as "full" or associated partner – See NeMo UI

- NeMo coordinator adds new Business partner
 - Full or associated

How to join NeMo as "full" or associated partner – See NeMo UI

- NeMo coordinator adds new Business partner

– See form

Marketplace: Business Partners

Business Partner Information

* Required fields

Partner ID *

Registered Name *

Company Name *

Address *

Postcode *

Website *

Phone *

How to join NeMo as "full" or associated partner – See NeMo UI

- NeMo coordinator adds new Business partner

– See form

Business Partner Additional ID

* Required fields

BP Type *

BP Value *

BP Description *

BP Contact *

BP Email *

BP Phone *

BP Website *

BP Address *

BP Postcode *

BP City *

BP Country *

BP VAT Number *

BP Tax ID *

BP SIC Code *

BP NACE Code *

BP Legal Form *

BP Registration Number *

BP Registration Date *

BP Registration Authority *

BP Registration Country *

BP Registration Status *

BP Registration Validity *

BP Registration Expiry *

BP Registration Renewal *

BP Registration Renewal Date *

BP Registration Renewal Authority *

BP Registration Renewal Country *

BP Registration Renewal Status *

BP Registration Renewal Validity *

BP Registration Renewal Expiry *

BP Registration Renewal Renewal *

NeMo Marketplace - Login

NeMo Login

Username or email *

Password *

Log in

NeMo Marketplace - Navigation

IBM © Service Prosumer Thomas Wutz Technical Administrator

Marketplace Business Partners

Business Partners Services Service Offerings Service Categories

Search

IMA Change your services and E-mobility services...	ESP Energy Storage for...
IRA As a research partner for the automotive sector...	GRIVY Power electronics platform operating in Europe...
IBM IBM Deutschland Health partnership in the R...	ICCS ICCS supports the NeMo Alliance industry...
MINDAC Mindac Energy SE is an SME specialized in...	INCLIRA The Production of Fuel is an industrial process...

NeMo Marketplace – Role info

IBM © Service Prosumer Thomas Wutz Technical Administrator

Marketplace Business Partners

User Role = Technical Admin

Node Role = Service Prosumer at IBM Node

NeMo Marketplace – How to search for a service

Marketplace Services

Business Partners Services Service Offerings Service Categories

Via „Services“ Tab

Enter search text – will filter on Name, Category – Searching for eRooming

Select Service of interest

NeMo Marketplace – View service details – GetLocations SOAP Service

Service Type: SOAP

Specification URL

Semantic description

NeMo Marketplace – View service details – IBM Trustee REST Service

Service Type: Webservice

Specification URL e.g. YAML

Semantic description : OWL file

Access Ctrl info: API Key

NeMo Marketplace – Service offering

Service Offerings

Search for Offerings by Gireve

NeMo Marketplace – Select offering

The screenshot shows a service offering page for 'SVC1 data-oriented service'. Callouts point to various parts of the page:

- Service infos regarding active and dates offering**: Points to the 'Status' and 'Offering Dates' section.
- Service offering for service GetLocation**: Points to the 'Service Offering' table.
- Here we have 2 variants to select from**: Points to the 'Variants' table.

Name	Description	Price	Currency
Variant 1
Variant 2

NeMo Marketplace – Signing a Service contract

The screenshot shows the 'Sign Contract' page. Callouts point to key elements:

- Sign Button on Service Details**: Points to the 'Sign Contract' button at the top right.
- Enter contract info relevant for you**: Points to the 'Contract Info' form fields.
- ACCEPT Button becomes active to sign contract**: Points to the 'ACCEPT' button at the bottom.

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IBM Cloud™ Monitoring with SysDig

- Operational visibility into the
 - Performance and
 - Health of the applications and services
- Full stack telemetry
 - Auto-collects metrics and events from various containers
- Alerts
- Notifications through channels
 - Email
 - PagerDuty
 - Slack
- View and design dashboards
- Explore entire environment

NeMo SysDig Dashboard

Thank you!

Thomas Walz
 Technical Relations Executive
IBM, Germany
Thomas.Walz@de.ibm.com

VCARD

[12:05] - Registration of an atomic or horizontal service. Service offering and contracting, Thomas Fousse (GIREVE) – Technical Demonstration

REGISTRATION OF AN ATOMIC OR HORIZONTAL SERVICE
SERVICE OFFERING AND CONTRACTING

Thomas FOUSSE

Project manager
GIREVE
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Register a NeMo service

Register a NeMo service

Register a NeMo service

Register a NeMo service

Register a NeMo service

The screenshot shows a registration form for a NeMo service. The form includes fields for Name, CIM Location, Description, CIM Location, Status, Active, and Web Services. It also contains several URLs and a table with columns for 'Average Power (kW)' and 'Average Available Capacity'.

Service Name	Active	Average Power (kW)	Average Available Capacity
GIREVE @ GDE...	Yes	0	0

Request a NeMo service

Request a NeMo service

Create a service offer

EVIC Data Annotated service

This is a commercial offering to get EVIC data

Address

Company Name:

Telephone Number:

17102018:

00101010 - 11001010

City:

Country:

ICID:

ICID:

Deliverables

Package List

Package:

Description:

Type:

Charging Station:

Address:

Name	Description	Price	Currency
EVIC Data Annotated	EVIC Data Annotated	100	EUR
EVIC Data Annotated	EVIC Data Annotated	100	EUR
EVIC Data Annotated	EVIC Data Annotated	100	EUR

Package:

Description:

Type:

Name	Description	Price	Currency
EVIC Data Annotated	EVIC Data Annotated	100	EUR

Thank you!

Thomas FOUSSE
GIREVE

[12:20] - Creation of a composite service: Charging point search based on mobility needs, Nils Masuch (TUD) – Technical Demonstration

COMPOSITE SERVICE CREATION

Nils Masuch
Technical University Berlin
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Agenda

- Overview Service Creation Tools
- Composite Service Creation
- Deployment & Testing
- Service Description Modelling

Overview Service Creation Tools

Service Development Tools	
Service Modelling	Semantic Service Model (Transformation)
	Semantic Service Description Tool
	Data Translation Mapping Configuration
Service Composition	Service Finder Tool
	Service Composition Tool
	Service Process Management Tool
Service Testing	Service and Service Composition Testing

Overview Service Creation Tools

Overview Service Creation Tools

Overview Service Creation Tools

Composite Service Creation – Actor/Use Case Creation

Composite Service Creation – Example Use Case

Composite Service Creation – BPMN Process Editor

Composite Service Creation – Search Service

Composite Service Creation – Search Service

Composite Service Creation – Search Service

Composite Service Creation – Process Integration & Finalization

Composite Service Creation – Process Integration & Finalization

Service Process Deployment

Service Process Testing

Service Modelling – CIM Model

- Common Information Model to describe services within NeMo
- Available in different representation languages
- For semantic descriptions, Web Ontology Language (OWL) format is used

Service Modelling – Description Tool

- Define all relevant parameters, such as Input, Output, Preconditions, Effects

Service Modelling – Description Tool

- Define all relevant parameters, such as Input, Output, Preconditions, Effects
- Comes along with a rule editor to specify restrictions under which circumstances a service is invocable

Conclusion

- Composite service has been created, tested, described and deployed
- Next Steps:
 - create translation file between proprietary model and CIM model (next presentation)
 - register service at marketplace (shown before)
 - Invoke service from outside the Service Creation Tools (next presentation)

Thank you!

Nils Masuch
Technical University Berlin

***[12:35] - Service execution, with focus on Integration bus and Translators,
Thodoris Theodoropoulos (ICCS) – Technical Demonstration***

SERVICE EXECUTION, WITH FOCUS ON INTEGRATION BUS AND TRANSLATORS

Thodoris Theodoropoulos
ICCS
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

Agenda

- NeMo-wide execution system architecture
- Service invocation
- Composite service invocation

Architecture

NeMo-wide execution system architecture

Public API
Integration Bus – Consumer Side

- REST API call reception
- Access control
- Service lookup
- Service routing

Private API
Integration Bus – Provider Side

- Service translation
- Service invocation

API call reception

- The chain of requests starts here
- Developer friendly interface to familiarise with api calls (swagger)
- Receive the API call on the consumer side
- API call is formatted in CIM (Common Information Model)
 - Promotion of interoperability

Access control

- IDAM (Identity access management) service on each node ensures access to local NeMo node instance
- OAuth 2.0 access control ensures access on the basis of a valid client-id and client secret.
 1. Create client application credentials
 2. Receive credentials
 3. Provide them to the client application
 4. Invoke IDAM with client credentials
 5. Receive token
 6. Provide token to the integration bus
 7. Check that the token is ok

Service lookup-rooting

- Lookup service in the registry-marketplace
- Find out the producer's nemo node ip
- Forward the call through a secure connection (via mutual TLS)
 - Only trusted NeMo nodes can reach each other!

Service translation

- Before execution

Service translation

- CIM model of the request body is translated to a proprietary model before invoking the service
- Proprietary model is translated to a common information model after invoking the translator
- Inventory of multiple objects

Grid EVs Charging Business

Service invocation

- Service is finally invoked on the provider side.
- Response is backwardly propagated through the network
- Both REST and SOAP invocation type supported
- Multiple service authorisation types supported

Composite service invocations

- API call made through the respective integration bus interface
- BPMN engine process process the call and invokes it
- Demo; Three service composite service
 - Get charging point locations
 - Estimate the SoC required to fulfill a given trip
 - Estimate the most probable charging stops according to historical profile and the initial SoC

Node Invocations

Thank you! Any Questions?

Thodoris Theodoropoulos
ICCS

[12:50] - Demonstration of a use case: Neutral server and Extended Vehicle standard integrated with the NeMo infrastructure, Roberto Tola (CRF) – Technical Demonstration

NEUTRAL SERVER AND EXTENDED VEHICLE STANDARD INTEGRATED WITH THE NEMO INFRASTRUCTURE

Roberto Tola

Centro Ricerche Fiat, Italy
Final Conference and Exhibition
19th September 2019

CRF Reference architectures

Beginning of NeMo

CRF Reference architectures

End of NeMo

IBM Neutral Server aka "Trustee"

Motivation

The CRF/IBM Trustee PoC

Main objectives

- Propose a real use case that impacts the EVs context
 - Prove the feasibility of the use case with the actual technology making evident the values for the users
- Integrate the OEM (FCA) with Trustee
 - Try the technology of Neutral Server/Trustee server, validating the related model
- Have a reusable result within NeMo context
 - Implement a use case reusable and compliant with NeMo context

The CRF/IBM Trustee PoC

Approach

Focused on the fulfilment of the EU "guiding principles" and on Data Privacy with its "double consent" approach

Overall architecture

Italian test site scenario

- Contract signature (app)
- Double consent (portal)
- Trip Starting (simul)
- CP2 booking (app)
- Road works queue (simul)
- Battery low warning (app)
- CP rebooking (from CP2 to CP1)
- Battery Recharging (simul)
- End of trip (simul)

The EV

The HMI

Charging points

Susa - TecnoSitaf

IRETI - IREN

The CourtesyAssistant app

Thank you! Any Questions?

Roberto Tola
Project Manager
Centro Ricerche Fiat, Italy
Roberto.tola@crf.it

For more information:

NeMo Project Coordinator:

Dr. Angelos Amditis,

Research Director

Institute of Communication & Computer Systems (ICCS)

9 Iroon Politechniou Str.

GR-157 73 Zografou, Greece

a.amditis@iccs.gr

<http://nemo-emobility.eu>

Hyper-**N**etwork for **e**lectro**M**obility

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